

A man wearing a wide-brimmed straw hat and a light-colored, long-sleeved shirt stands in a wooden boat on a calm river. He is looking out over a vast landscape of rolling green hills and a wide expanse of water. The scene is bathed in the warm, golden light of a sunrise or sunset. In the foreground, the wooden structure of the boat is visible, including a dark buoy hanging from the side. The background shows layers of hills receding into the distance under a hazy sky. In the top left corner, there are green leaves and branches of a tree. The overall mood is peaceful and contemplative.

Brazil - Piauí Rural Development Project Fisheries Component

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World Bank AGREP Division Working Paper No. 106 Economics and Policy Division -
Agriculture and Rural Development Department - June 1981

Cover and Layout: Gonzalo Castellón Grime

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Component**

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SUMMARY AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The Fishery Sector in Brazil

i

With an exclusive economic zone of over 610,000 km², about 80% of Brazil's total annual fish production is obtained from the sea. Fisheries have supplied the country with nearly 805 thousand tons in 1979, up from 430 thousand tons in 1967; today, the artisanal and industrial subsectors share this total production almost equally. In 1978, while agriculture contributed nearly 3%, the fishery sector contribution to the GNP was only 0.31%. SUDEPE-PDP has estimated that by 1990, Brazil will be producing nearly 1.6 million tons of fish. Natural resources are estimated to be rich, although their availability varies according to regions and fish species. The Northeast is considered to be the area with the most abundant fish resources. Fish is consumed fresh and processed (e.g., salted, dried). Brazil has one of the lowest indexes of per capita consumption at 4.8 kg compared with a world average of 13.1 kg per capita. The North and Northeast regions are potentially the largest consumption centers; most constraints faced today are related to marketing and distribution (paras. 1.1-1.5).

ii

Recent studies have estimated nearly 600,000 fishermen of which 400,000 are devoted to artisanal fisheries. It has also been estimated that another 200,000 families are directly or indirectly depending

on fisheries for their livelihood. The artisanal fishery sector is very important from the viewpoint of domestic consumption, employment and rural development. Fishermen are organized in colonias and in cooperatives, the coops being the next, more advanced, step from the colonias. By the end of 1979, there were 24 cooperatives in the country, grouping nearly 2,200 fishermen. These coops have grown slowly due to the lack of organization and economic / financial resources (e.g., credit) (paras. 1.6-1.12).

The Fishery Sector in Piauí

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Piauí's coastal fisheries are at the subsistence level with a fairly good potential for achieving, in the near future, higher levels of income and welfare.. The State of Piani possesses a coastal line of 66 kilometers. Unlike the States of Ceara, Paraiba and others to the South, the States of Maranhao and Piaui region has resource endowments which enable development programs with a high degree of confidence that the fish resources will be able to sustain the proposed changes in the quantity and quality of the fishing effort (parai. 2.1-2.9). This region supports a much higher biomass than other regions in Brazil, and that biomass is composed of a higher population of large fish. In sum, it is said that the region has the highest biomass with the lowest utilization rate.

iv

There are 2,219 fishermen within the ten most important fishing communities in Piauí, of which 1,208 are solely dependent on fisheries for their livelihood and 1,011 fishermen devote part of their time to fisheries and part to other activities, particularly agriculture. There are several unorganized fishermen's colonias in the state and one cooperative: Luis Correia (COPELCO). At present, the coop has 105 members and operates only with very small financial assets. Other forms of organization include informal groups; there are 7 of these, each of them consisting of 60 fishermen. Fishermen incomes are low, and fishing villages are very poor. The technology used by artisanal fishermen is rudimentary. There are three types of vessels: canoes, sailboats and motorboats. In the state there are 132 canoes and sailboatn and 24 motorized vessels. The most important types of fishing gear used are line and hook, nets and traps. The most common nets used in the region are gillnets and cast nets. In 1978 the state produced 3,249 tons of fish and 1,015 tons of mangrove crabs; 65% of this total fish production comes from marine fisheries, of which 80% is produced by artisanal fishermen. Red snapper, king mackerel, sea bass and tarpon make up the bulk of the catch. The average catch per fisherman is very low on per capita basis, i.e., 843 kg per year or 2 kg per day. One factor which explains this low production level is the high ratio of fishermen per boat there are too few boats for too many fishermen. Consequently, the number of effective fishing days (or income) per fisherman is very low. Given the productivity of existing technology, using average of 6 persons per family, and excluding the small number of boat owners frqm the total population, fisheries-

related income of each family member averages US\$63 per year. Only 7% makes more and 60% makes less than the average. Future increases in income will depend on the availability of fish resources, the quantity and quality of fishing effort, and the ability of the system to improve marketing and distribution (paras.. 2.10-2.41).

v

Fish, shrimp and mangrove crab are processed in several forms. Processing at the household level is one of the most important activities of the sector and represents an important source of income and employment for the fishing family. Shrimp and mangrove crab are processed at the village level, using rather simple processes: salting, cooking, drying, smoking and fermenting. Though consumption surveys are not available, it is evident from current statistics that fish consumption is high and will continue to grow at a fast rate. Marketing is very active (intra- and interstate-marketing) where products are classified in three classes. Within each class, the fish are sold in bulk and paid one price for each class rather than a price for each type of fish (paras. 2.42-2.57).

vi

There are several activities which are vital to the development of the fishery in Piauí, namely, shipbuilding, mechanical services and supply of ice. The total number of shipbuilders is approximately eight; they are located along the coast and use mostly hand tools. Retail outlets, located in Parnaíba, supply engines and mechanical assistance. Present capacity for ice production is limited, particularly in coastal areas; POLONORDESTE is financing for COPELCO a small ice factory whose production capacity

is being set at 8 tons/day (paras. 2.58-2.62).

vii

There are institutional as well as noninstitutional sources of credit. Noninstitutional sources are tied to marketing arrangements; a middleman supplies credit to the fishermen for purchasing bait, repair of gear and for other purposes (usually family related, e.g., health). Institutional sources of credit through which development funds are channeled include Banco do Brasil, Banco do Nordeste, Banco do Estado do Piauí and Banco Nacional de Crédito Cooperativo. Funds are allocated based on the rules and procedures stated in the Rural Credit Manual (paras. 2.63-2.71).

viii

Extension and technical assistance is executed by EMATER-PI which has staff located in Parnaíba and Luís Correia since 1976. During the period 1976-80, 52 fishermen received some type of technical assistance in fishing technology, fish marketing, and organization. Financial resources applied in the area of fisheries extension and technical assistance is very low, although these funds have increased from US\$15.1 per family in 1975 to US\$24.1 in 1979 (paras. 2.72-2.77).

The Role of This Project Within the Brazilian Context

ix

Several important characteristics make this project rather unique within the Brazilian rural development context. First, the project puts a major emphasis on a group who depends on fisheries for their livelihood: the fishermen. This group is extremely important since it not only produces and supplies an important source of animal protein to the rural poor, but its development is important for a geopolitical viewpoint, namely, geographic decentralization and development presence in coastal areas. Second, the project would benefit artisanal fishermen and their families, and therefore is formulated in such a way that it can be replicated in other areas of Brazil; particularly other Northeastern states. Third, the project has been designed in a way to minimize the use of very scarce energy resources, specifically the use of petroleum-based products. There is a lower limit to the use of these resources which is imposed by the location of fish resources and by the need for appropriate fishing gear. Finally, this project offers a development concept for advancing very underdeveloped fisheries to higher levels of sophistication with minimum disruption to social institutions. Specifically, this project offers a technological path which includes three well-known technological options: traditional sailboats, improved sailboats and motorized sailboats, all of which are actually being used in the area. Although it must be recognized from the outset that such an approach would have to be improved, as we

gain experience in implementing the proposed project, it represents an important framework for Brazilian artisanal fisheries development.

Long-Term Development Options

x

The major contribution of fisheries to development comes through the generation of higher income levels, the production of food and the creation of productive employment. Consequently, two of the basic goals of fishery sector policy is to improve the welfare of low-income fishing families by increasing their productivity and to meet domestic needs by supplying large amounts of relatively cheap animal protein to low-income consumers in both rural and urban areas. In this respect, the economic and social development of small-scale fisheries has become a major concern in Brazil today. The development of this type of fishery can contribute to both a fuller and, sometimes, more economical utilization of existing resources and to an increased productivity of a population that has fishing as its only or main source of income and welfare.

xi

In developing an individual fishery, a balance needs to be ascertained among various stages of such activities as catching, processing and marketing. The establishment of adequate marketing and distribution systems to reach low-income consumers is essential

xii

Within this long-term perspective, it is difficult to predict the time it will take for an underdeveloped fishery to move to higher levels of technology, nor is it possible to outline with certainty all the factors which will be responsible for a change in the rate at which transformation will take place. However, the rate of urbanization will transform marketing and production toward satisfying higher levels of demand for fresh fish. In addition, the nature of extension and training is expected to change as different fishermen groups advance to different levels of technology. Furthermore, income levels and income distribution is expected to change, although after five or six years, the rate of change should decrease. Finally, the village life-style will change as the productivity of the fishing family increases as a result of this project; from subsistence, the village is expected to move to a more active cash economy (paras. 3.1-3.18).

The Project

xiii

The main objectives of this project are: (a) to increase the income of the fishing family and (b) to increase the amount of animal protein available to low-income consumers; The project is expected to lift several development constraints, the most important are related to production, marketing and organization. Other constraints are related to shipbuilding, extension and training, processing and land tenure (paras. 4.2-4.10). In lifting those constraints, the project will adopt a strategy

which aims at achieving the following principles: (a) self-reliance, (b) improvement of income distribution, (c) resource conservation and management, (d) development through rationalization rather than modernization, and (e) institutional development. To achieve the previously stated objectives and strategy, the project will provide: (a) credit to fishermen to purchase fishing vessels and several types of fishing gear; (b) equipment for the coop including working capital; (c) extension, training, technical assistance; (d) research and experiment; and (e) consulting. Total project cost is estimated at Cz\$338.5 million (US\$6.05 million; US\$1 - Cz\$56). This estimate neither includes price nor physical contingencies. The project would be implemented over a period of five years starting in 1981. Evaluation will take place at the end of the second year, and a redefinition of project activities, based on effective progress, may take place (paras. 4.11-5.7).

xiv

As in the case of the marketing component, an agency, namely, SUDEPE, has been assigned the planning, coordinating and part of the execution of the fisheries component. Besides the banking system, which in a way will execute the credit component, two other agencies will be responsible for the execution of the project: EATER (extension, technical assistance, training) and OCEPI (coop management) (paras. 6.1-6.12).

xv

Two major changes in project design took place during appraisal: (a) downsizing the quantity of fishing effort, and (b) redesigning the

extension and technical assistance component. The main reason being to focus mainly on low-income fishermen and improve the efficiency of extension services in the fishing villages (paras. 8.1-6.3). To rationalize the overall development within the fishery sector and progressively benefit the largest number of fishing families, several technological options are offered by the project, all of which are well known in the area. These options are presented in a typology of boat models which uses three technological levels: (i) traditional sailboat, (ii) improved sailboat and (iii) motorized boats. This typology represents the basis for the financial and economic analysis of the project (paras. 4.32-4.35).

xvi

At full development in about 1986, the project's annual incremental production would be about 6 thousand tons of fish valued at US\$4 million on the basis of September 1980 dollars. Long-term marketing prospects for the project output look good (paras. 7.1-7.6). The fish produced will be consumed both in and out of the state. The economic rate of return of the project is expected to be 35% (paras. 8.7-8.15).

I. THE FISHERY SECTOR IN BRAZIL

1.1

With an exclusive economic zone of over 610,000 km² and 9,000 km of coastal line, 80% of Brazil's total annual fish production is obtained from the sea. The fishery sector has achieved a growth rate much lower than the average for the country; for example, in the period 1966-77, the country grew at a rate of 10.8% while fisheries did at a rate of only 5.9%. The fishery sector in Brazil, although locally important, is not of great importance in the context of the whole economy; in 1978, fishing sector contribution to GNP was 0.31%, while agriculture contributed nearly 2.6%. Fisheries have supplied the country with nearly 860 thousand tons of fish in 1978, up from 103.3 thousand tons in 1939. Production varies according to geographical regions (see Table 1-1) Of this total, 50.4% comes from the artisanal fisheries sector. Among the most important species caught, the following can be singled out: sardines (22%), croaker (10%), crustaceans (11%), shrimp (7.7%) and lobster (1%). SUDEPE-PDP (Program for Research and Development of Brazilian Fisheries) has estimated that by 1990, Brazil will be producing nearly 1.6 million tons of fish (including other products; see. Table 1-2)¹.

1.2

Brazil's international trade of fish has become a significant source of foreign exchange in the last few years. Although the industry held an average deficit of nearly US\$12 million (1967-75), it became a net

¹ There are 300 major water reservoirs in Brazil with an estimated potential of 800 thousand tons of fish, if aquaculture is developed properly. This report puts little emphasis on aquaculture, given the coastal nature of the project under consideration.

exporter by 1976, with a positive net balance of US\$11.5 million in 1978. The growth in exports seems particularly promising; while in 1978

Table 1-1: TOTAL FISH PRODUCTION IN BRAZIL, BY REGION, 1967-77 (ton)

Year	North	Northeast	Southeast	South	Midwest	Total	Growth Index (1967=100)
1967	51833	134262	113506	107740	2081	429422	100
1968	68332	135351	154032	140445	2227	500387	116
1969	70252	129747	163584	135601	2013	503166	117
1970	53778	133095	154321	182811	2287	528262	122
1971	58020	139597	190184	201895	1847	593514	138
1972	55168	139046	207596	201788	1080	606650	141
1973	60150	148878	222672	266128	974	700775	163
1974	110354	147242	249092	222227	2393	733282	170
1975	128614	164016	230534	234666	1962	761767	177
1976	105313	140991	197351	212977	2215	660823	153
1977	126912	159810	221886	240323	3676	754584	175

Source: IDB.

Table 1-2: PRODUCTION PROJECTIONS OF FISH IN BRAZIL, 1980-90 (ton)

		1977	1980	1985	1990
1. Marine Fisheries					
Fish		804784	606714	824358	985000
	Pelagic	255964	-	430938	550000
	Demersal	168928	-	213420	225000
	Other	79892	-	180000	210000
Crustaceans		69512	77622	93297	105000
	Shrimp	51237	-	54497	60000
	Crab	10766	-	30000	35000
	Lobster	7509	-	8800	10000
Mollusks		5708	15000	25000	30000
Mammals		4120	-	-	-
Algae		-	8925	20000	40000
	Subtotal	584124	708261	962655	1160000
2. Freshwater Fisheries		168483	183674	212096	230000
3. Aquaculture		22000	30000	80000	200000
	TOTAL	774607	921935	1254751	1590000

Source: SUDEPE-PDP.

export trade reached the US\$50 million mark, preliminary estimates for 1980 put this mark up to US\$200 million. Lobster (41%), fresh and frozen fish (31%) and shrimp (23%) are the most important export products (see Table 1-3).

Table 1-3: EXPORTS AND IMPORTS OF FISH, FOR BRAZIL, 1966-1978

Year	Export		Import		Balance
	Quantity (tons)	Value (US\$ '000)	Quantity (tons)	Value (US\$ '000)	Value (US\$ '000)
1966	3078	5372	31667	17704	-12332
1967	3507	5823	45692	27533	-21710
1968	6247	10738	54191	28807	-18069
1969	9572	20192	61781	27626	-7434
1970	10403	19384	62565	34989	-15605
1971	12245	27180	52328	34114	-6934
1972	18845	39841	39924	33300	+6191
1973	18747	35602	57645	54287	-18985
1974	17117	48147	49952	59068	-10911
1975	16977	43488	109982	60716	-17228
1976	15259	54459	79375	53050	+1409
1977	26400	74778	64827	54613	+20165
1978	50900	83100	126800	71600	+11500

Source: SUDEPE, CACEX and FAO.

1.3

Fishery sector activities have developed slowly. In the past, where fishing was almost artisanal except for those fisheries located close to expanded urban centers, major development bottlenecks were, and still are, marketing and distribution: the perishability of fish and

sea products, the distances to consumption centers, and the lack of infrastructure and appropriate transport.

1.4

The fishery sector law (Código de Pesca) was enacted in 1934 and, although rather old and under revision, it single⁴ out for the first time the importance and public recognition of the fishery sector in Brazil. Several years later (1961-62), the Council for Fishery Sector Development (CODEPE) and the Superintendencia de Pesca (SUDEPE), under the Ministry of Agriculture, were created with the view to accelerate the development of fisheries. These agencies passed Law 221 in 1967, which defined several economic incentives for the fishery sector. The period between 1963 and 1967 was characterized by intensive planning. The diagnosis arrived at during that period was used to formulate taxes and subsidies incentives to increase private sector investment in the fishery sector, all of which had rather positive results. In 1965, production was only 370 thousand tons, while today it is 805 thousand tons, and exports grew from US\$16 million in 1966 to US\$105 million in 1978. However, the incentive program, which financed 173 projects with a cost of Cz\$1.8 billion through 1973, had several problems: (a).some projects were overdesigned with regard to the availability of existing resources--for example, projects to catch sardines were designed to capture 600,000 tons when the resource can sustain only 200,000 tons; (b) most funds are allocated within the processing sector and not in the fishing activities, creating an excess capacity and economic inefficiencies--51Z of total funds were

allocated to the processing industry, 29% to fishing activities (e.g., vessels),-13% to administration and only 7% to marketing; and (c) the majority of funds were allocated to industrial rather than artisanal fisheries where the largest majority of fishermen belong.

1.5

In particular, by 1979 Brazil had 340 processing industries with 3,611 tons of freezing capacity per 24 hours and a cold storage capacity of 64,600 tons. SUDEPE has estimated that the annual utilization rate of such capacity is only 30%; efficiently used processing industries reach 45 to 60%. The canning industry is working at 50% of its capacity. A detailed information on these industries is provided in Table 1-4. Policy trends have now emphasized the development of artisanal fisheries due to their impact on employment, domestic consumption and geographic decentralization. Five major programs have been initiated since 1979: (i) increase available lines of credit, including both domestic and foreign sources of funds; (ii) establish a price support system, namely, minimum prices, for 47 fish species of low value; (iii) establish a fish distribution scheme for the 47 abovementioned species through the rede somar (COBAL) to supply fish to low-income people in urban areas; (iv) impose a unique tax system for petroleum-based products; and (v)

Table 1-4: ACTIVITIES CARRIED OUT BY PROCESSING INDUSTRIES

Type of Activity	Number of Factories
Chilling	201
Freezing	130
Salting	104
Canning	47
Smoking	8
Seaweed Processing	8
Fishmeal and Oil	44
Ice Plant and Cold Storage	200

Source: BID.

establish a housing program at the fishing village level. The results of such programs are not known yet.

Resource Endowments in Marine Waters

1.6

During colonial times (1649), Matias Beek, a Dutchman, wrote in his diary that fishermen were catching an average of 300 fish per week; most of which of very large size. The total biomass of demersal fish for all of the Brazilian coast (between 0 and 199 meters) varies from 1,116 thousand tons to 1,512 thousand

tons. Although statistics are sparse, it has been concluded that a sustainable yield could approximate 50% of the calculated biomass. The location and productivity (by specie) of such biomass have to be carefully considered. The major biomass of demersal fish is found in the North and South regions, varying from 494 thousand tons to 715 thousand tons and from 409 thousand tons to 567 thousand tons, respectively. With regard to pelagic resources, the maximum sustainable yield has been estimated at 900 thousand tons, where fish resources are more concentrated in the Southeast and South regions.

Human Resources

1.7

Since statistics are very deficient, it is rather difficult to estimate the number of fishermen. Recent studies have estimated that there are nearly 600,000 fishermen in Brazil, of which 400,000, or two thirds, are devoted to artisanal fisheries. It has also been estimated that an additional 200,000 families are directly or indirectly depending on fisheries for their livelihood. The new Código de Pesca defines artisanal fisheries as those fishing enterprises that are carried out by an authorized professional fisherman, by himself or with the help of his family, using

traditional fishing methods and vessels of less than 20 gross tons. They possess nearly 40,000 small vessels, which are constructed at the local level by artisanal shipbuilders. Artisanal fishermen have developed slowly, and some of them have even been forced into other activities because of: (a) changes in technology which are less labor-intensive (i.e., an increase in the capital / labor ratio), (b) increases in the marginal productivity of other sectors, and (c) speculation with existing lands where fishermen live (explained in para. 2.16). The Brazilian artisanal fishery-sector, despite its backwardness, represents the most important domestic suppliers of fish. Compared with the southern part of the country, most artisanal fishermen are located in the Northeast (54%).

1.8

Other fishermen are engaged in industrial fishing. The capacity of the industrial fishing fleet varies according to methods used (see Table 1-5). The trawl fleet (employing double-rig, otter, pair and stern trawls) which operates in the southeast and southern regions comprises 310 boats of an average age of 11 years, 70% of which have wooden hulls. Catches consist mainly of croaker, weakfish and shrimp. The trawl fleet in the northern

region comprises 144 units of an average age of 8 years, almost all having steel hulls; catches are shrimp and catfish. The fleet of purse seiners is mostly concentrated in the south with 291 boats, having mostly wooden hulls, with an average age of 18 years. The purse seiners catch sardines, mackerel, bluefish and mullet. There are 124 units devoted to shrimp fisheries, with an average of 7 years per boat. Finally, there are 116 boats using line methods, having mostly wooden hulls, with an average age of 10 years; these boats harvest high-quality fish. These large-scale fishery vessels are vertically integrated with the processing industry that employs a considerable amount of labor, mostly located in the south of the country (see Table 1-6).

Table 1-5: INDUSTRIAL FISHING FLEET¹
(Ships with more than 10 gross ton capacity)

Type of Vessel	Number of Units	Average Tonnage	Total Tonnage
Handliners (North)	64	107	6828
Handliners (South)	52	51	2668
Lobster (Northeast)	124	42	5181
Seiners	291	47	13674
Trawlers (North/Northeast)	144	105	15098
Trawlers (Southeast/South)	310	79	24529
TOTAL	985	69	67978

¹There are approximately 20,000 fishermen and boat owners involved in industrial fisheries (Source: National Plan, 1980-1985).

Source: FAO/IDB.

Table 1-6: LABOR EMPLOYED IN THE PROCESSING INDUSTRIES, 1975-1976

States	Labor	% Workers	% Administrative Personnel
Rio Grande do Sul	4300	90.7	9.3
Santa Catarina	3249	91	9
Parana	54	81.5	18.5
São Paulo	4000	87.5	12.5
Rio de Janeiro	4788	87.7	12.3
Espirito Santo	147	84.3	15.7
Bahia	310	87.1	12.9
Sergipe	-	-	-
Alagoas	49	77.6	22.4
Pernambuco	76	77.6	22.4
Paraiba	300	87	13
Rio Grande do Norte	718	87.5	12.5
Ceara	2275	86.9	13.1
Piaui	20	90	10
Maranhao	53	77.4	22.6
Para	1023	88.4	11.6
Amazonas	146	89	11
TOTAL	21508		

Source: IDB.

Regional Distribution of Production

1.9

Among all regions, the South and Southeast regions of the country contributed to nearly 63% of total production during 1968-77. The Northeast region contributed only 23%, with a decline to 21% since 1973. The contributions of the remaining

regions are rather small. The level of exploitation of different species also varies according to regions. For expositional purposes, the level of exploitation of different fish species can be divided into three: (a) intensively exploited, (b) moderately exploited, and (c) underexploited. The most extensively exploited species are highly correlated with their commercial value: in the North, plramutaba and pirarucu; in the Northeast, lobster and red snapper; in the Southeast, pink shrimp and deepwater prawn; and in the South, croaker, hake, white hake and mullet (most of which are rather competitive with Uruguayan and Argentinean fisheries). Among the moderately exploited species, one finds courade and tambagui in the North; serra, kingfish and mangrove crab in the Northeast; and catfish, anchovy and harvestfish in the Southeast/South. Anchovy, tuna# pelagic fish and some crustaceans are considered underexploited species.

Consumption

1.10

National average fish consumption in Brazil is low by international standards, but it could increase considerably if marketing and distribution systems are improved (FAO, 1979). Per capita

supply of fish has been estimated at 7.4 kg/year, nearly half the world average of 13.1 kg/year. There are no recent marketing studies to draw upon in determining actual consumption levels¹. Over 95% of the total catch is consumed domestically, more than half after some form of processing, in particular, salting, drying or canning. Internal distribution of fresh fish tends to be concentrated in coastal areas and in the large urban centers of Sao Paulo and Rio de Janeiro, and other major cities (this pattern is typical of many Latin American countries). There are wide divergencies in regional consumption levels; there are potentially large consumption centers, particularly in the interior of the country. Although the North and Northeast regions are not the country's top fish suppliers, most locally processed salted/dried fish in Brazil is marketed mainly in those areas. The composition of different types of fish and fish products depends on the distance between production and consumption centers, ability to dispose of a very perishable marketing surplus, and infrastructure available for marketing and distribution (e.g., transport, ice, cold storage). The overall supply of ice plays an important role in this respect. In Brazil, the static capacity of the existing ice industry was 1,350 thousand tons annually by 1979, while actual production was approximately 900 thousand tons

¹ Aditonal information is presented in the section on "Marketing and Prices." See also Annex VII.

per year. Most of these ice factories are vertically integrated with the processing industry which is located mostly in the South. Consequently, if one considers the abovementioned regional differences as well as a 2 to 1 ratio of ice to fish production, there are many areas where this input is seriously constraining the expansion of markets. CIBRAZEM (Empresa Brasileira de Armazenamiento) manages many wholesale posts in several states (a list is presented in Table 1-7).

Organizational Arrangements

1.11

From the viewpoint of employment and domestic consumption, artisanal fisheries still play a leading role. Although the artisanal fisheries subsector had the longest participation in production, this relationship has changed in the decade of the 1970s. The development of those fisheries has been constrained by lack of training, slow transfer of technology, lack of access to large consumption centers, lack of credit to increase as well as replace the existing fisheries effort, and lack of protection and enforcement (i.e., land tenure at the village level and keeping industrial fisheries out of the three-mile fishing zone).

Table 1-7: MARKETING UNITS AND WHOLESALE OUTLETS FOR FISH, FOR BRAZIL

State / City	Name of Unit	Category	Capacity (m ³)
MA	São Luiz	Entrepasto de Pesca	857
CE	Fortaleza	Entrepasto Dragão do Mar	514
	Aracaju	Posto de Recepção de Pescado	x
	Mudaú	Posto de Recepção de Pescado	x
RN	Natal	Entrepasto de Pesca	343
	Bahia Formosa	Posto de Recepção de Pescado	x
	Caíçarás	Posto de Recepção de Pescado	x
PB	João Pessoa	Entrepasto de Pesca	103
	Bahia da Traição	Posto de Recepção de Pescado	x
	Pitimbo	Posto de Recepção de Pescado	x
PE	Recife	Entrepasto de Pesca	5000
	S.J.,Corca Grande	Posto de Recepção de Pescado	x
	Ponta da Pedra	Posto de Recepção de Pescado	x
AL	Maceió	Entrepasto de Pesca	600
	Penedo	Posto de Recepção de Pescado	x
SE	Aracaju	Entrepasto de Pesca	143
BA	Ilhéus	Posto de Recepção de Pescado	x
	Camboa do Morro	Posto de Recepção de Pescado	x
RJ	Rio de Janeiro	Entrepasto de Pesca	3885
	Angra dos Reis	Fábrica de Gelo P.Pesca	x
SP	Santos	Terminal Pesqueiro	2571
	Cananéia	Entrepasto de Pesca	x
PR	Paranaguá	Posto de Recepção de Pescado	x
SC	Coqueiros	Posto de Recepção de Pescado	x
RS	Porto Alegre	Entrepasto de Pesca	x
	Rio Grande	Entrepasto de Pesca	x
	S.Lourenço do Sul	Posto de Recepção de Pescado	x
	Iratí	Posto de Recepção de Pescado	x
PA	Soure	Entrepasto de Pesca	x
SC	Laguna	Terminal Pesqueiro	x

¹This is a very old ice factory located in the fishing terminal.

Source: IDB.

1.12

There are fishermen who are owners of the existing boats and gear, others who only possess some gear and still others who neither possess boat nor gear--they offer their labor. The distribution of fishing proceeds is done in parts, where a certain percentage is assigned to the boat/engine, another to the gear and a final portion goes to the fishermen (a detailed breakdown is given in para. 2.37). The owner of the boat usually supplies the food, ice, bait, gear and other inputs.

1.13

Artisanal fishermen in Brazil have a very poor standard of living and are confronted with several problems related to health, nutrition, housing and hygiene. They are organized in colonias and in cooperatives. The colonias are very weak organizations which do not receive much technical assistance, credit and support for infrastructure. By the end of 1979, there were 24 cooperatives in the country, considered the next step to the colonias; these coops grouped nearly 2,200 fishermen (the number of fishermen who belong to coops has increased). Overall, there are at least two types of problems with the development of coops: (a) financial--principally lack of credit for investment and working capital

(capital de giro) and marketing infrastructure (e.g., transport); and (b) organizational--principally, the lack of a national policy toward coops, the fishermen's lack of coop mentality, and a weak administrative capacity. The characteristics described before are more or less the same for all artisanal fisheries in Brazil.

II. PIAUÍ'S FISHERIES TODAY

Resource Endowments

2.1

Piauí's coastal fisheries are at the subsistence level with a fairly good potential for achieving, in the near future, higher levels of income and welfare, given proper planning and execution of development schemes.

2.2

The State of Piauí possesses a coastal line of 66 kilometers. This coastal line lies between the States of Maranhão (the Parnaíba River being the boundary) and Ceará. Unlike the States of Ceará, Paraíba and others to the south, the State of Maranhão and Piauí have resource endowments which permit development programs with a high degree of confidence that the fish resource

will be able to sustain the proposed changes in the quality and quantity of fishing effort. Some of the elements that define this degree of confidence are presented below.

2.3

Because data for the State of Piauí is lacking, this report outlines and explores the available data on fish resources in the whole Northeast and more specifically for the total coastal area off Piauí and Maranhao. Marine waters off the Northeast, are formed by a mass of tropical waters coming from the Guyana and Brazil currents and a mass of subtropical and antarctic currents going from the south to the north in the Atlantic Ocean. The tropical waters have an average temperature of 25°C and salinity of 36.65‰ to 36.90‰, with a depth of up to 200 meters. The subtropical waters are much colder, where temperatures range from 9°C to 12°C and salinity is an average of 36.18‰ in a depth between 130-200 meters and 600-700 meters. Finally, the Antarctic waters have an average temperature of 5.5°C with a salinity of 34.40‰ at a depth of 500-700 meters.

2.4

The primary productivity of these waters is around 50g C/m

/year and a standing crop of zooplankton which does not go over 150g C/m² /year. The continental platform of the Brazilian Northeast is relatively narrow. For the Piauí State the coastal zone covers an area of 1,247 sq.mi., divided in: (a) between 0-20 m, 397 sqmi.; (b) 20-50 m, 532 sq.mi.; and (c) 50-100 m, 318 sq.mi. (see Table 2-1).

Table 2-1: CONTINENTAL SHELF, BY DEPTHS
(in square miles)

Regions	Depths (in meters)			Total
	0-20	20-50	50-100	
Maranhao	4881	10663	5960	21504
Piauí	397	532	318	1247
Ceara	4656	4412	2471	11539
Rio Grande do Norte	2150	1311	358	3819
Parnaíba	380	660	100	1140
Pernambuco	417	933	174	1524
Alagoas	609	1494	286	2389
Sergipe	400	496	203	1099
Bahia	2788	7796	3963	14547
Northeast	16678	28297	13833	58808

Source: Hydrographic and Navigation Division, Ministry of the Navy, Brazil.

2.5

The areas adjacent to the Parnaiba River's delta are rather rich in nutrients and have extremely high biological productivity.

2.6

According to a resource assessment study undertaken by SUDENE in 1976¹, among all of the Northeast states only the States of Maranhao and Piaui have significant marine resources capable of further exploitation. This resource assessment study divided the Northeast in four regions: Region I, Maranhao and Piaui; Region II, Ceara, R.G. do Norte and Parnaiba; Region III, Pernambuco, Alagoas, Sergipe and Bahia; and Region IV, Offshore Banks and Islands. The study noted first that Region I supported a much higher biomass than any other region, and second that the biomass was composed of a much higher proportion of large fish (mostly in offshore sharp areas between 50-100 meters).

2.7

The potential for increase in total catch varies within the Northeast (see Table 2-2). The highest biomass density with the lowest utilization rate is found in Region I (see Table 2-3), while the lowest biomass density with the highest utilization

¹ SUDENE, Fishing Terminals in Northeast Brazil, The Economist Intelligence Unit, London, 1976

rate is found in Region III. Stock assessment related research in the Northeast has estimated the sustainable yield of several species with the following results: (i) cavalla, 3,500 tons for a fishing effort of 5.5×10^6 hooks/day (Ceara only); (ii) jerra, 4,100 tons for an effort of 8.1×10^6 hooks/day (Ceara only); (iii) peixevoador, unknown); (iv) Atuns, unknown; (v) Lagosta, 8,800 tons for an effort of 18.8×10^6 covas/day; and (vi) pargo, 5,800 tons for an effort of 12.8×10^6 hooks/hour. These figures are very tentative, and with the exception of shrimp (Lagosta), catch for most fish species are well below their MSY.

Table 2-2: PRESENT LANDINGS AND LIKELY SUSTAINABLE YIELD, BY REGIONS
(tons per year)

	Landings	Likely MSY Over 20 cm Fork Length	Over 20 cm Fork Length
Region I	25252	233836	202882
Region II	41168	33628	23642
Region III	14870	18904	10656
Region IV	1000	-- 17271 (All) --	

Source: SUDENE, Fishing Terminals in Northeast Brazil, The Economist Intelligence Unit, London, 1976, p. 29.

Table 2-3: UTILIZATION OF BIOMASS, BY REGION

	Region I	Region II	Region III
Average Biomass Density (tons/km²)			
Total	18.19	6.9	3.33
Mean Length 7.20 cm	15.87	3.15	1.49
Mean Length 7.25 cm	13.49	1.49	0.84
Average Rate of Exploitation			
Tons/km ² /year	0.43	0.96	0.29
Percentage Utilization of Biomass			
Total	2.36	13.91	8.71
Mean Length 7.20 cm	2.71	30.48	19.46
Mean Length 7.25 cm	3.19	43.44	34.52

Source: SUDENE, Fishing Terminals in Northeast Brazil, The Economist Intelligence Unit, London, 1976, p. 29.

2.8

Although evidence shows a considerable abundance of fish resources in Region I, the study seems to have underestimated the total biomass available for capture. Two major reasons account for this: first, the resource assessment study was based on acoustical survey techniques, which neither provide an estimate of the resource within five meters of the surface¹ nor an estimate of those actually in contact with the ocean floor².

¹ For example, mackerel and dolphin.

² For example, shrimp and lobster.

Second, no sampling was conducted within five miles off the shore.

2.9

Some of the abovementioned estimates were taken from the preparation report. As established later on in this report, a stock assessment study is proposed as part of this project.

Fishing Technology

2.10

The technology used by artisanal fishermen is rudimentary. There are three types of vessels: canoes, sailboats and motorboats (see Table 2-4). The canoes are very small and used mainly as transport devices for mangrove crabs and as the base for cast-net fishing. The canoes are generally planked craft with ribs, measuring some 3.5 to 6 m. They are propelled by poling or rowing.

2.11

The sailboats can be divided into two groups: (a) 6-meter sailboats that are mostly used during winter times when winds do not constitute a high risk of damage; and (b) 7- to 8-meter sailboats

Table 2-4: NUMBER OF FISHING VESSELS¹

Type	Year	1974	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979
A. Rowboats and sailboats		22	23	39	46	63	132 ²
B. Motorized vessels					3	9	24

¹The sharp differences between 1978 and 1979 may be explained by changes in survey methods.

²There are 74 sailboats (see para. 2.36).

Source: EUTER-PI.

which are devoted to the catch of tarpon during the summer when there are strong winds. The sailboats are round-bottomed sailing skiffs. These are outfitted with cotton sails which are typically made by the fisherman himself; the sails normally last about six months. Sawn frames and butted planking, fastened with iron nails, are beginning to be adopted. The steaming of planks and frames is rare. For this reason, bows and sterns are generally truncated. The wood is generally tarred outside and left bare inside the boat. The keels on the canoes and sailing skiffs are recessed into the frames while the planking is butted up to the keel. Only a little bump protrudes from under the boat. This arrangement offers the least resistance when, upon return, the boats are beached. Unfortunately, this design also makes for a highly unstable boat, and the fishermen indicate that in

fact boats capsize quite often during the summer when the winds are strong. Rather than take undue risks, they rarely fish on windy days, thereby foregoing considerable production.

2.12

The masts are not permanently mounted in the vessels but rather are stepped and stayed each day as the sail is rigged. The total sail area is 20 m² on the average boat. On average, four fishermen operate these sailboats where beside the gear no other inputs are used (i.e., ice). Space limits the number of pontas¹ and the amount of ice these vessels can hold. Actually, each fisherman uses, on average, nets of 9 pontas (see Table 2-5).

2.13

The small motorized vessels have been introduced very recently. The existing extension and training program is partly responsible for this (see para. 2.72). The motorized craft are of two types. First, the motorsailer, which is the predominant type. This type of boat is typically 8-9 m long, with a deck and a half-cabin, powered by an 11-hp Agrale air-cooled, 1 cylinder diesel, with the same type of sprit sail arrangement as used on the sailing skiffs. The

¹ A "ponta" is a measure of length which corresponds to a section of net about 30 m long. The height of these nets is normally around 28-30 meshes. About 15 pontas of netting per man is considered a good amount of gear to fish.

Table 2-5: POSSESSION OF GEAR BY TI AND TP FISHERMEN¹

		TI (%)	TP (%)
Own Gear			
I. Castnets		17.5	50.5
II. Handlines		28	26.7
III. Gillnets			
	1-5 Pontas	9.1	23.8
	6-10 Pontas	12.6	13.9
	11-15 Pontas	4.2	5.9
	16-20 Pontas	9.8	2
	21-30 Pontas	12.6	3
	> 30 Pontas	3.5	1
Own No Gear		33.6	15.8

¹These figures have been revised by the preparation team and, consequently, there might be some difference with the percentages presented in the main text. Also, some fishermen may own more than one piece of gear and, consequently, these columns may add up to more than 100%.

Source: SUDENE, Fishing Terminals in Northeast Brazil, The Economist Intelligence Unit, London, 1967.

construction is also similar to the sailing skiffs, but the keel 'construction includes a skeg which, along with an added beam, gives this craft a good deal more stability than the sailing skiffs. These motorized vessels have isothermic ice boxes which can carry up to 3 tons in the small ones and up to 6 tons in the larger ones. Four to five fishermen operate the boats.

2.14

The most important types of fishing gear used are line and hook, nets and traps. Fishing for red snapper (Zargo) is executed with hand lines, each of which has several baited hooks. Average fishing depths are 60 fathoms. On the smaller boats, due to the lack of “free board” (height of deck above the waterline) and low deck railings, the lines are hauled by hand. These lines generally have seven to ten baited hooks.

2.15

The most common nets used in the region are gillnets and cast nets. The gillnet currently used in Piauí is very effective since it is usually made of monofilament nylon which, when new, is invisible to the fish. However, this net needs replacement since, after several years, the material turns a milky color and presumably is no longer invisible to the fish. Each piece of gillnet is nearly 30 m long with a maximum height of 30 m, and they have a mesh of 5-8 cm. The gillnet for tarpon (eggaru in) fisheries is a little bit different: length of 100 m, height of 2.5 m and mesh of 20-22 cm. The cast nets have a round bottom, 2 m in diameter. These nets are mostly used for shrimp fishing or for catching bait. The cast nets (tarrafas) used in the coastal and lagoon

fishing in Piauí are hand-knit, monofilament nets with a diameter of about 3 m fully extended. Their design is basically the same as that of the cast nets used in shrimp fisheries the world over. These cast nets are used by a fisherman working alone in shallow water, sometimes standing in a small boat, but it can also be used from the shore or while wading. The net is circular and is thrown by moving the arms and upper body in an arc and releasing the net in such a way as to make it open up in the air and fall down, encircling a column of water. Both shrimp and fish are caught with this type of gear.

2.16

There are many types of traps, mostly homemade and used in several fishing activities.

2.17

There are no good studies about the productivity of existing fishing gear. Field trips and surveys during 1980 resulted in an estimated average productivity for gillnets of 2.65 kg/ponta/day (with a maximum of 3.65 kg/ponta/day). With regard to the productivity of hook and line, these surveys found a productivity of 2.8 kg/hook/day, considering an average effective time of 9

hours per day.

The Fishing Community

2.18

Within the ten most important fishing communities (see map 1)¹, there are 2,219 fishermen, of which 1,208 are solely dependent on fisheries for their livelihood (working part- or full-time) - these are called Tempo Integral (TI) - and 1,011 fishermen who devote some time to fishing and some time to other productive activities, particularly agriculture--these are called Tempo Parcial (TP). Those ten communities are located in two municipalities, namely, Parnaíba and Luís Correia where the fishermen population represents approximately 8% of the economically active labor force (see Table 2-6).

2.19

The Piauí artisanal fishermen are linked to three types of organizations; two formal-colonias and the cooperative--and one informal--"groups" of fishermen. In the coastal area, there are five colonias: Luís Correia, Cajueiro, Barra Grande, Morros do Mariana and Parnaíba. Although legally all fishermen must

¹ A total of 14 fishing villages, each with nearly 200-300 fishermen, has been estimated.

LEGEND

- Fishing landing place
- ⊙ Controlled Fishing landing place

MAP 1 - Coastal Zone - Piauí - Brazil

Table 2-6: NUMBER OF FISHERMEN IN THE TEN LARGEST COMMUNITIES

Fishing Village	Population	Fishermen		
	Total	TI	TP	Total
Barra Grande	1142	247	120	367
Barrinha	265	62	50	112
Cajueiro	1800	191	233	424
Carnanbinha	82	50	10	60
Catandugas	1165	40	60	100
Coqueiro	535	66	77	143
Luis Correia	3414	240	120	360
Macapá	200	26	5	31
Morros do Mariana	3476	147	215	362
Pedra do Sal	545	139	121	260
Total	12624	1208	1011	2219

Source.* Preparation Report.

Table 2-7: NUMBER OF FISHERMEN ASSOCIATED IN THE COLONIAS (1975)

Colonia	Number of Fishermen
Cajueiro	160
Barra Grande	380
Luis Correia	480
Parnaiba	369
Morros do Mariana	150
Total	1539

belong to those colonias, only 1,539 belong to them (see Table 2-7). These colonias are like guilds; they provide some social services for their members, such as medicine and death benefits, and they make sure everyone is registered at the social security office and the post captain's office. Sometimes, these colonias lobby for the artisanal fishermen's interests in Teresina (the state's capital) and in Brasilia. However, they do not engage in direct economic activity.

2.20

There is one cooperative in the area--Cooperativa Mista Reional de Pesca do Luis Correta (COPELCO). A critical assessment of today's COPELCO activities and future programs are presented in the next section.

2.21

Finally, the fishermen are associated in informal groups through which they receive some technical assistance. There are a total of 7 groups in the municipalities of Parnaíba and Luís Correia, each of them consisting of 60 fishermen. Other members of the fishing families, particularly housewives, are also grouped to receive technical assistance to develop nonfishing activities as an additional source of income; e.g., artisanal products, food production and social services.

2.22

Despite these different forms of organizations, the fishing communities are poor. Houses are made of light material, and roads, electricity and other social infrastructure (e.g., health post, water supply) are very poor, if they exist at all. Some of these villages are not even connected by access roads, and one needs to walk across the beach for several hours to reach them.

2.23

Two main reasons explain such a phenomenon: (a) the level of income in the community--most fishermen earn very little (see paras. 2.33-2.41); and (b) the fact that they cannot reinvest in

the village (e.g., house improvement) nor can the municipality due to the fact that the fishing families do not own the land they live on. This latter issue needs some further explanation.

2.24

Most of the land belongs to the Patrimônio da União (the government), not only the land on which fishermen live but also the agricultural land whose boundaries are set by the “high tide” in the area. First, since they do not own the land, fishermen are not allowed, and do not have the incentive, to improve their houses. They are only allowed to build with light materials like straw, palm fronds and the like. No improvements such as latrines, permanent wells or cement houses are permitted. Second, since this land does not legally belong to the community, fishermen cannot request the municipality to bring into the village electricity, improved roads and streets, health services, and so forth

2.25

The lack of roads has constrained transport and marketing and, consequently, development and income. However, in the areas where access roads have been built, land speculation has taken place because of tourism; high-income groups have easier

access to lease the land, build expensive houses, and little by little push the fishermen out of their activities. This phenomenon is not new in Brazil, and authorities are seriously trying to avoid it in Piauí.

2.26

Once the land is allocated, roads can be built and expected increases in income due to the project are expected to be reinvested in the fishing village.

2.27

As of now, houses do not have any type of sanitary equipment, and even drinking water is obtained without using filters. Education is deficient; those villages that have a primary school do not have enough classrooms to serve the population. Health services are nil, most of the people with serious diseases have to reach large towns where conditions are much better. The Extension Service is training women for first-aid procedures. Additional information is presented in Table 2-8.

Table 2-8: SOCIAL CONDITIONS OF FISHING COMMUNITIES (percent)

Type of Fishing Village	House							
	Walls			Letrine		Source of Water Supply		
	Very Light	Light	Adobe	With	Without	Well	Public Well	Shallow Well
Coastal	6.1	90.8	3.1	12.2	87.8	36	7.9	56.1
Estuarine	30.3	64.5	5.2	14.5	85.5	59.2	1.3	39.5

The Cooperative: COPELCO

2.28

The only cooperative in the area--Cooperativa Mista Regional de Pesca do Luis Correia (COPELCO)--was founded in 1972, failed to function for several years and was reactivated in 1979. The coop is located in Luis Correia municipality, but its jurisdiction includes also fishermen from Parnaiba and Buriti dos Lopes. The main objectives of this cooperative are to stimulate the overall development of the subsector, particularly marketing (local and out of state) of fishery products. The coop is supposed to perform several such economic activities as input supply, fish handling, transport, processing, marketing and distribution. Also, an important objective of the coop is to train the fishermen in areas related to cooperativism, management, legality and organization.

2.29

At present, the cooperative has 105 members and only operates with very small financial assets. These assets as well as several activities (i.e., training and management) are being expanded through several programs. One of these programs is POE/

POLONORDESTE: Programa Operativo Especial para o Estado do Piauí and the POLqNORDESTE Program in the Delta do Parnaíba project. POE/POLONORDESTE is financing the construction of several receiving posts located in Morro da Mariana, Pedra do Sal, Coquairo, Barra Grande, and Cajueiro. These posts are small havens that have an area for receiving and handling the fish, four freezers, and a small cold storage area with a four-ton capacity. At headquarters, the program is financing the construction of a building which would include administrative offices, an ice factory (8 tons/ day), a storage facility (25 tons), a cold storage (17 tons) which will function at -7 C, and a small refrigerated truck to supply ice to the receiving posts and collect and transport fish from each village to headquarters. All these facilities are expected to be in operation by the end of 1980.

2.30

Another program for technical assistance is executed by OCEPI and now also being financed through the POLONORDESTE/DELTA project. The need for technical assistance and training was assessed by a group of institutions¹ coordinated by CEAG/PI, the Centro de Apoio a Pequena e Média Empresa. The program includes the financing of management staff for a period of

¹ Including EMATER, BNCC, INCRA, SAPI

one year and the supply of technical assistance in the fields of administration, legality, accounting and auditing. The manager of COPELCO has already been hired; he has a good knowledge of fishing, marketing and extension.

2.31

CEAG identified problems in four major areas: (a) administrative/organizational--where most problems are related to the lack of an organigram (functional responsibilities), an efficient control system, an adequate management and auditing structure, and an appropriate informational system; (b) production--where most problems are related to the poor effectiveness of the cooperative to capture a large proportion of existing fish production (including its own members); (c) socioeconomic--where most problems are related to the lack of control over, and the inappropriate system of, collecting and paying the required capital, and the lack of operating capital; and (d) financial--where most problems are related to payments to fisherman, improving relationships and increasing the number of members, and competing as an input supplier (including credit) with other agents in the system.

2.32

These programs are of fundamental importance to the development of artisanal fisheries in Piauí. These programs are timely and will have a major impact on fishermen's welfare. However, some of the infrastructure provided (e.g, ice plant) will not be sufficient to absorb the changes in the quantities of effort, particularly those envisaged by the project, and need to be expanded. The technical assistance program will continue through 1980, and should be picked up by the project from 1981 onwards. It is difficult to assess the impact of such new programs, although there is no doubt that they are badly needed, particularly before the start of the proposed project.

Fishermen's Production and Income

2.33

Total production of fish has not stayed constant since 1974 (see Tables 2-9, 2-10 and 2-11). With its short shorelines and with a rather rudimentary artisanal sector, the state has produced 3,249 tons of fish and 1,015 tons of mangrove crab in 1978. Of the total fish production, 65% comes from marine fisheries (i.e., 1,686 tons).

2.34

Red snapper, king mackerel, sea bass, and tarpon make up the bulk of the catch. As stated earlier, most fish are caught in gillnets and fish weirs and on hand lines. Snapper and grouper are the main species caught on hand lines. As in the case of other fisheries, production is seasonal (see Annex III, Figures III-1 through III-11). Shrimp are caught with castnets, while mangrove crabs are caught by hand. No trawling, purse saining, light fishing or long-timing is done at all in Piauí.

2.35

The total catch is very low on per capita basis, partly due to the high subsistence nature of the fisheries. If one excludes the mangrove crab production carried out by 200 fishermen, the average production per year comes at 843 kg per fisherman, or 2.3 kg per day. Assuming that a fisherman keeps nearly 5 kg per day, a total of 7.3 kg/fisherman/day is still extremely low.

2.36

One factor which explains this low level of production per fisherman, and thereby income, is the high ratio of fishermen per boat. The number of effective days of fishing is very low;

approximately 150 days per calendar year. Of a total number of 2,219 fishermen, 1,208 are TI and 1,011 are TP. The number of TI fishermen is divided into 140 mangrove crab fishermen, 156 fishermen who use castnets, 359 without boat and gear, 473 who possess only gear, and 80 boat owners (56 sailboat and 24 motorboat owners). The number of TP fishermen, on the other hand, is divided into 60 mangrove crab fishermen, 150 who neither possess boat nor gear, 454 who own some type of gear, 329 who are castnet fishermen, and 18 sailboat owners.

Table 2-9: FISH PRODUCTION IN PIAUI (in tons)

Years	Total Fish Production ¹	Coastal Fisheries	
		Artisanal	Industrial
1974	3200	897.4	393.2
1975	3669	1057.4	339.8
1976	3874	423 ²	548.7
1977	3249	1067.9	598.1
1978	3249	1686	425 ³

¹Includes freshwater fish.

²Only second semester.

³This includes only frozen fish.

Source: SUDEPE, Fisheries Statistics, 1977, 1978.

Table 2-10: BREAKDOWN OF MARINE AND ESTUARINE CATCH STATISTICS¹ FOR 1977²

Name		January-June Catch (M tons)	July-December Catch (M tons)	Total
Fish				
	Arazimbort (Jack) (Caranx Laus A.)	12928		12928
	Bagre (catfish) (Various species)	30426	27705	58131
	Cason (Shark) (Various species)	22747		22747
	Camaurupin (tarpon) (Tapon Atlanticus)	0	64852	64852
	Camurin (Centropomus)	34424		34424
	Cavalla (mackerel) (Scomberomorus Cavalla)	19920		19920
	Golosa (Genvatremus Luceus)	13315	13656	26971
	Guaiuba (Like snapper) (Ocyrus Chrysurus)	37977	30489	68466
	Pargo (red snapper) (Lutianus Purpurtus)	175833	155525	331358
	Pescada-Cascuda (sea bass) (Cynoscion Acoupa)	38184	19878	58062
	Serra (king mackerel) (Scomberomorus Mocolatus)	22425	13524	35949
	Jamarajana Acu (mullet) (Mugil Incillis)	12145	19774	31919
	Larau Branco (jack) (Caraux Hippos)	23927		23927
	Other and unidentified lish	135276	143147	278423
	Subtotal	579527	488550	1068077
Tortoises				
	Subtotal	1221	569	1790
Molluscs and Crustaceans				
	Camarao (shrimp) (Trachyoenaeus)	17281		17281
	Caranguejo (mangrove crab) (Ocides Cordatus)	300564	347817	648381
	Other	4406	13302	17708
	Subtotal	322251	361119	683370
	TOTAL	902999	850238	1753237

¹An indeterminate, but small, proportion of the catch is missed due to two factors:

1) some of the newer, motorized boats -particularly in the Serra Grande areas- market their catch out-of-state;
2) some of the really small communities have no statistics gatherer.

²Statistics for 1978 exist and show a total catch of 1832 metric tons for the year, much the same as the 1977 statistics shown here. The 1977 statistics are used because the available data for 1978 does not have as good a breakdown of species.

³Not broken down in statistics for second half of year

Source: SUDEPE/PDP.

Table 2-11: MOST IMPORTANT COASTAL PRODUCTS FOR 1978¹ (in tons)

Species	Production	% of Total
Mangrove crab	1015.5	55.7
King mackerel	61.9	3.4
Sea bass	52.4	2.9
Catfish	50	2.7
Camurin	38.2	2.1
Tarpon	37.8	2.1

¹The relative importance is defined in volume terms. In value terms, shrimp is the most important product.

Source: PDP/SUDEPE, 1979.

2.37

The accepted system for distributing the proceeds is: 25% to the boat and motor, 25% to the gear and 50% to the fishermen.

2.38

Given the productivity of existing technology (see cash flow models), an average of 6 persons per family, and excluding the boat owners, each family member is making an estimated net average cash income of US\$63 per year (this is a weighted average). The income distribution structure is highly correlated with the number of effective fishing days, ownership of existing

means of production and the time devoted to fishing (see Table 2-12). Today, among the four fishermen who use a sail boat, typically one is the owner of the boat/engine and part of the gear, another owns the other part of the gear, and two supply only labor.

2.39

The POLONORDESTE Program defines their rural sector target group in terms of MVRs (one MVR = Cr\$2,480.2); the program channels funds only to those who earn less than 200 MVRs. With the exception of those who own motorized boats, all the fishermen are making less than one fourth of this requirement, and a large majority are making even less than one twentieth. The MVR limit was originally designed to deal with farmers, and it does not always apply to fishermen. The main reason has to do with the common property nature of fish resources and with the biological nature of those resources. While increases in productivity by small farmers on their private properties has little or no effect on the productivity of other farmers, increases in productivity by one fishery may have profound negative effects on other fisheries. In addition, expansions in productivity are limited by the biological sustainability of the resource;

expansions beyond the MSY result in important future losses in income to all. Consequently, the expansion of fishing effort--thereby increasing the productivity of individual fishermen--has to be implemented by changes in the size and quality of the available technology. In particular, by increasing the number of motorized vessels, In this case, then, in order to increase the real income of the majority of fishermen, one must accept the fact that some fishermen will earn a little over 200 MVRs.¹

2.40

Future increases in income will depend on the availability of fish resources, the quantity of fishing effort (number of boats, horsepower, fishing days), the quality of that effort (motorized boats and improved gear), extension and training, and the ability of the system to improve marketing and distribution.

2.41

For some families, fishing is not the only source of income. As stated earlier, the TP fishermen devote part of their time to agriculture, and it is expected that the majority will continue to do so. These fishermen / farmers are mostly concentrated in

¹ In terms of net income, this income level might be much lower. See cash flow tables. This statement assumes and recommends private ownership of vessels. Cooperative as well as collective ownership of vessels is not desired, due to conflicts in dealing with effective operation and maintenance.

Table 2-12: NET INCOME WITHOUT THE PROJECT¹ (dollars per family)²

Type of Fishermen ³		Family Income (US\$)	Number of MVRs	Per Capita Income
1	M _i T _i	9120	207	1520
2	o ^T M _i	2342	53	390
3	V _i T _i	2272	52	378
4	V _i T _i P	1988	45	331
5	A _i T _i V _i	376	9	62
6	o ^T V _i	215	5	36
7	o ^T PV _i	154	4	26
8	A _i T _i PV _i	133 ⁴	3	22

¹This table will be subject to further revisions.

²This represents average rent at constant prices (1980 = 100).

³1 = owners of motorized boats

2 = fishermen with no gear who work in M (all)

3 = owners of sailboat who devote all their time to fishing

4 = owners of sailboat who only devote their time partially to fisheries

5 = fishermen who possess gear; who work on a sailboat and who are devoted only to fisheries

6 = fishermen who do not possess gear, who work on a sailboat and who are devoted only to fisheries

7 = fishermen who do not possess gear, who work on a sailboat and who devote themselves only partially to fisheries

8 = fishermen who possess gear, who work on a sailboat and who devote themselves only partially to fisheries

⁴A_iT_iPV_i fishermen have lower income than o^TPV_i fishermen because of their large number and the ratio of fishermen with and without gear in any given sailboat.

¹This table will be subject to further revisions.

estuarine areas. They rent small plots of land, and their cropping patterns are similar to those of other farmers in the state, namely, they produce rice (the principal crop), maize, beans and mandioc. A survey was carried out by the preparation team; copy of the survey questionnaire is presented in Annex VII. The average yearly income has been estimated at Cr\$42,000 (equivalent to US\$125 per capita), with investments in hand tools approximating Cr\$1,000 (every 2 years) and operation and maintenance of nearly Cr\$83,000 (see Annex VII). The income earned here is equivalent to a little over five months of work. Although most of

these fishermen/farmers expressed that fishing activities are more profitable (perhaps as an expression of cash income more than real income), it is expected that they will continue in agriculture. In addition, agricultural activities do not conflict with fishing activities. There are important reasons for not discouraging such mixed production patterns: (i) culturally they have been doing this for centuries; (ii) the food produced has a great stabilizing impact, particularly in isolated fishing villages where there is very little inflow of food items; (iii) because these fishermen can devote time to agriculture, they also play a stabilizing role on fish prices - during the harvesting season, when prices are low, they devote their time mostly to agriculture, thereby reducing further increases in fish supplies and avoiding decreases in prices, and (iv) "keeping the door open' to agriculture enables horizontal integration of fishing activities with those other activities carried out in rural areas - as technology is introduced, and thereby capital-labor ratios increased, there might be a real potential for the displacement (in the far future) of some fishermen. If those circumstances prevail, those fishermen will have the opportunity to intensify agricultural production activities.

Processing

2.42

Large quantities of fish, shrimp and mangrove crab are processed in several forms. In the industrial sector, Piauí has only one industry: Industria Pesqueira de Ceara (IPECEA). This factory is located in Luis Correia and is integrated with several large industrial vessels since 1974. The processing capacity of the industry, for shrimp, pargo and lobster, is three ton per day (mostly shrimp) and mostly developed for export markets. IPECEA possesses the only cold storage/freezing facilities in the area with a stock capacity of 200 tons; this capacity is used exclusively for the factory's production. It also possesses an ice plant with a production capacity of 15 tons per 24 hours. The factory employs a total of 100-150 people, and its administration is located in headquarters (Jortaleza, Ceara). An undertermined number of artisanal fishermen sell their produce to IPECEA. Those fishermen are provided with ice, isothermic boxes, food, gasoline and, sometimes, some working capital at low prices. This situation is expected to change when COPELCO is equipped to provide these and other important services to fishermen. The most important of those services is the supply of ice.

2.43

However, processing at the household level in Piauí is one of the most important activities in the sector, particularly the processing of shrimp and mangrove crab. This sector represents an important source of income and employment for the fishing family and will form an integral part of this project. The technology used in processing at the village level is rather simple; salting, cooking, drying, smoking and fermenting. The processing is rather effective, and the products last for a long time under existing weather conditions and with a practically nonexistent storage infrastructure. There are two types of agent who process shrimp, i.e., fishermen and middlemen: the latter group buys fresh from the fishermen and processes at home, they buy at Cr\$10 per kg. The transformation coefficient actually used is: 2.5 kg of fresh shrimp are equivalent to 1 kg of processed shrimp. There is a great difference in scale between processing by the fishermen and by the middlemen; while a typical fisherman unit processes approximately 5 kg per day, the middleman does 45 kg. In addition, given the differences in location between these two groups, there are also differences in inputs and output prices. The sales price at the village level is Cr\$65 per kg with an average cost of production of approximately Cr\$58.3 per kg.

The sales price at the middleman's level is Cr\$80 per kg with a production cost of Cr\$32.5 per kg. While a fisherman would earn US\$135 per year, the middleman would earn US\$9,200 per year (more than 60 times). Finally, these processed products are sold in urban centers, rural towns and villages. Since the price for fresh shrimp is higher than the price for processed shrimp, except during the harvesting season, there would be a trend to sell fresh shrimp except in rural areas. (For additional information, see Annex VII.)

2.44

The processing of mangrove crab is a very profitable business. Due to segmentation in marketing, the mangrove crab fisherman does engage in processing. The people who process the crab (we found two people in Parnaíba) are able to make significant amounts of money with a very low cost in processing. These crabs are cooked, the legs separated from the body, and crab meat and whole legs are sold as separate products. These products are sent to Fortaleza, Recife and other consumption centers in neighboring states. One processing unit can process 200-300 kg of crab meat and 300 dozen legs per week. The actual price of crab meat is Ct\$140 per kilogram. A cash flow

statement has been prepared which shows an annual net revenue of over US\$4,000 (see Annex VIII).

2.45

Fish products like fish meal or other types like frozen products are not produced in the state. Improving the physical capacity of the system to produce those products, particularly through the existing coop will be extremely important. Today, during the peak of the harvesting season, there is a lot of third-class fish which is lost for lack of processing. Fishermen devote much more time to selling and preserving first- and secondclass fish than they do to very cheap, third-class fish (see para. 2.50).

2.46

Improvements in fish procesetng are necessary to stabilize (reduce the seasonality) 4shermen's purchasing power.

Consumption, Marketing and Prices¹

2.47

Although consumption surveys are not available for the State of Piaui, it is evident from current statistics that fish consumption

¹ Additional information on demand is given in section VII.

is high and will continue to grow at a fast rate. Several agencies have estimated an average per capita consumption of fish for the state; these estimates vary from 3.4 kg to 8.0 kg per capita per year¹. These figures are still below world average. After considering the overall fish production and exports in and out of the state, the Agricultural Planning Commission of the State (CEPA-PI) has estimated an apparent consumption of 16,245.5 tons for 1977, with a stated deficit of 12,933 tons².

2.48

Marketing of fish in the State of Piauí is very active, where fish are coming from within the state (salt- and freshwater fish) and from outside the state. As in many other places, marketing at the beach level is tied to money lenders. In Piauí, 10-15% of the marketing surplus is disposed of through the coop and IPECEA (mostly first-class fish). The existing middlemen and fishermen's wives dispose of the other part of the surplus. Fish are marketed several times before it gets to the final consumers (in or outside the state). A flow chart of the existing marketing structure is presented in Figure 2-1.

1 See, for example, Estudo Nacional da Despesa Familiar (ENDEF), Vol. V, Secretary of Planning, 1977.

2 For additional information, see Section VII.

Figure 2-1: MARKETING STRUCTURE.

2.49

Fish are classified in three classes: first, second and third, responding in part to consumers' preferences, availability and size of the fish, A list of fish belonging to each of these classes is presented in Table 2-13. Within any particular class, the fish are sold-in bulk and paid one price for each class rather than a price for each type of fish.

Table 2-13: CLASSIFICATION OF FISH

First Class	Second Class	Third Class
White tarpon	Sea Bass (-11, kg)	Catfish
Red snapper	Hake (-1 kg)	Bonito
Anchovy	Horse mackerel	Sardine
Hake	Grouper	Sharponse shark (-20 kg)
Sea bass	Frigate mackerel	
	Butterfish	
	Bream	
	Mullet	
	Jack	

2.50

The coop in Luis Correia, for example, buys first-, second- and third-class fish at Cr\$ 70, Cr\$40 and Cr\$25 per kg, respectively. These fish are sold in retail markets directly by the coop at Cr\$110, Cz\$60 and Cz\$35 per kg, respectively. This markup is set on the basis of past experience but is being revised on the basis of marketing and distribution costs. The volume this coop is selling today is rather small reflecting the lack of purchasing power and the low number of members.

2.51

The fish that are sold within the state-are mostly distributed through several retail markets in the state, particularly In Teresina, Piripiri and Parnaiba. Most of these retail outlets do not have adequate facilities to store the fish. In Parnaiba, the government is finishing the construction of two large wholesale markets; these markets will be provided with cold storage. As the day goes by, because of the lack of cold storage, the fish that is not sold is salted or repacked in tiny isothermic boxes with ice and sent to other minor markets within the large cities or in rural areas.

2.52

Given the perishability of fish products, price fluctuates during the year and during a day of sales.

2.53

Profit margins at the middleman, transport and wholesale levels are adequate, the total value depending more on the volume of sales (the scale of operation) than on the marginal profit rate. Overall markets are very competitive.

2.54

There are many middlemen who buy fish at the beach. They buy in small quantities, some of them using very primitive systems of transport (e.g., bicycle).

2.55

In those areas where a village has access to consumption centers through public transport, several women play the role of intermediaries, with the view of making at least a part of the total mark-up during the process. These women, or any middleman, need at least three types of input to market fish: ice, icebox (isothermic box) and transport. Ice costs Cr\$30 per block (a block is more or less 25 kg), an icebox costs Cz\$1,600, lasting a couple of months, and transport costs C43 per kg (from Barra Grande to Parnaiba). Transport cost from San Luis (State of Maranhao) to Teresina is more or less Cz\$23 per kg. However, a wholesaler from San Luis has to pay additional costs, and the cost of not selling the fish he brings from such long distances is very high.

2.56

Within the retail markets, fish is an important substitute of beef,

chicken, pork and mutton. In general, meat is much more expensive than fish. Fish consumption within the households vary depending on the location of the households and their income. Those living near the Parnaiba area consume much more fish than those living in rural areas or to the south of the state. Income elasticities are rather high (reaching two for some high-income groups), and expenditures on fish vary across income groups. However, low-income groups may, in some cases, eat more or less the same amount of protein as high-income groups, the difference being in the class of fish they eat and, consequently, in total expenditures.

2.57

For the fishery sector to develop, much more emphasis should be placed on marketing, particularly through the cooperative (see section IV). This requires important improvements of both the institutional and the physical aspects of marketing and distribution. It is important to note that the availability of transport and cold storage will have substantially positive price stabilization effects, particularly during the harvesting period. In addition, more adequate physical infrastructure will also improve the quality of fish over long periods of time, thereby

improving fishermen's incomes.

The Ancillary Industry

2.58

There are several activities which are vital to the development of the fisheries in Piauí, the most important being shipbuilding, mechanical services and supply of ice. Net making and repair, sail making and repair, and supply of food are carried out by the fishing family, and no problems are expected once the project comes into implementation¹.

2.59

Shipbuilding activities are extremely important for this project, since it is expected that changes will take place with regard to the quantity and quality of vessels. Shipbuilding in Piauí is done in several locations along the coast, using mostly hand tools. The total number of shipbuilders is approximately eight², and these builders are located in Pedra do Sal, Cal, Luis Correia, Coqueiro, Barra Grande, Cajuero and Parnaíba (2). The master builder works with two or three assistants. The state has good forestry resources to supply the industry with the necessary

¹ The project is expected to provide technical assistance to these activities (see para. 4.16).

² In large towns, namely, Luis Correia and Parnaíba, there are shipbuilders who occasionally devote time to this activity. Otherwise, they are employed in the construction or furniture business. There are plenty assistant carpenters.

wood, although competitive uses of forestry resources are driving prices up. The number of vessels each shipbuilder builds varies between 4 and 12 per year, depending on existing demand. The main constraint for those who only build four vessels per year is the type of hand tools used. The vessels they build vary from 3 m to 20 m long.

2.60

Fishermen in the area acquire engines from retail outlets located in Parnaíba. All the engines used in the project area are produced in Brazil, and they have a warranty for nearly a year after sale. The company also provides some nominal level of technical assistance in engine repair and maintenance. Given the actual number of motorized vessels and its moderate increase, this industry is not expected to become a bottleneck during project implementation.

2.61

The present capacity for ice production is limited particularly in coastal areas. With the exception of IPECEA, located in Luis Correia, all the other small ice factories are located in Teresina: Gelo Cristal (1.0 tons/day), Gelo Polar (15 tons/day), Fripisa

(6.2 tons/day) and J. Nelson (3.1 tons/day). The total capacity is little over 40 tons/day; however, average production is less than 50% of that capacity due to the type of technology used in production. Expansion of this capacity is minimal. In addition, given the distance from these factories to production centers (the closest beach is 350 km from Teresina), it is not expected that those factories will supply ice to the fishermen.

2.62

Today, POLONORDESTE is financing a small ice factory for the coop whose capacity is being set at 8 tons/day. This capacity is not enough and needs expansion.

Credit

2.63

The description and analysis of the overall credit system are given in the main report. This report is basically concerned with those aspects of the credit system that directly relates to the fisheries components.

2.64

As in many other countries, there are institutional as well as

noninstitutional sources of credit. The noninstitutional sources are tied to marketing and other productive activities; the middleman supplies credit to the fishermen for purchasing bait, repair of existing gear and for other purposes (usually family related; e.g., health). Data on volume and terms under which credit is supplied, using noninstitutional sources, are not available. In Piauí, the fishermen's dependency on money lenders seems to be rather weak because of the low cost of funds supplied by existing institutional sources of credit. However, the presence of noninstitutional sources of credit is expected to continue in the future.

2.65

There are several institutional sources of credit to fisheries, particularly for artisanal fisheries development. These sources are available to assist development programs intended to accelerate growth in agriculture where fisheries are included or to assist institutions directly involved in executing this development, i.e., the cooperatives. Most often, these sources of credit are executed through existing banks--Banco do Brasil (BB), Banco do Nordeste (BN), Banco do Estado do Piauí (BE) and Banco Nacional de Crédito Cooperativo (BNCC)¹--with close

¹ BB, EN and BE have agencies located in Parnaíba. BNCC has an agency in Teresina.

collaboration of the extension agency EMATER.

2.66

The funds available are allocated based mostly on the rules and procedures stated in the Rural Credit Manual. According to this manual, funds are made available, first, for short-term investments (credito para custeio) which include expenditures on fishing activities, maintenance of boats and gear, purchase of gear (e.g., nets, sails) and for the marketing and processing of fish (investments); second, for fixed investments like vessels, equipment and installations, building, etc; and third, for marketing, not only for expenses but also working capital (capital de giro). The terms and conditions vary with the type of investment. Since most of the funds for the project will come from the POLONORDESTE program, it is important to mention that the maximum amount of credit available to an individual fisherman cannot exceed the 100 MVR¹ where 1 MVR - Ct\$2,480.20) and cannot exceed 7,500 MVR for a cooperative. All credit lines are financed using an interest rate of 10% per year, which is highly subsidized given an annual inflation rate of over 100%. Vessels are financed with a repayment period of 8 years and 2

¹ The Rural Credit Manual here is subject to interpretations, since the credit limit of 100 MVR is applied to investments to improve the land but not for land itself which is considered a fixed asset. In fisheries, fishing vessels should and are being considered by some as equivalent to land. Legally, vessels are also defined as fixed capital. To avoid potential delays, the terms and conditions for vessels that cost more than 100 MVRs have been agreed to and are presented in Section V, para. 5.5.

years grace; short-term investment with 2 years and no grace; equipment with 12 years and up to 5 years grace; and working capital (capital de giro) with 120 days, no grace.

2.67

In order for an individual fisherman to obtain financing, several prerequisites have to be met: (a) fishing has to be his main activity, (b) the fishermen must possess a license, (c) he must have paid the regular fees and commitments to the colonia, and (d) he must have been authorized by the Navy to fish.

2.68

With regard to collateral, Banks are not requesting collateral for loans that are below 100 MVR. For those loans that go over such a limit, as with motorized vessels, the investment. (boat, engine and gear) is used as collateral.

2.69

Most, if not all, of the credit applications are prepared and supervised by MATER, the extension agency. This procedure has facilitated the overall process and has minimized risk in repayments. Repayment is nearly 100%. EXATER prepares an

application which is discussed with the respective Banks and follows up the process through the repayment period. The relationships between EATER and the Banks are excellent. This system is found to be appropriate and is expected to continue.

2.70

Credit statistics collected by EMATER are rather complete. Available statistics usually are presented for the agriculture sector as a whole where fisheries appear as a hidden component. Nevertheless, some statistics on credit to fisheries are available; an outline follows. EMATER has 83 local offices dealing with credit, of which 2 local offices are allocating credit to fisheries; the other 81 are dealing exclusively with agricultural credit. The average value of loans to fishermen are smaller than those for agriculture in the State of Piauí. These statistics show that while in 1979, fishery sector loans represented 1% of the total, fishery sector loans in 1980 (until August) have climbed to 2.25%, more than double. The productivity of those local offices dealing with fishery credit is much higher than those offices assigned to agriculture.

2.71

The Banco do Brasil has a very active credit program in the fishery sector, although it is very small compared with credit allocations to agriculture. This program has grown from 18 loans in 1977 to over 98 loans in 1980. In contrast, the total amount of long-term agricultural credit for the Parnaíba and Luís Correia municipalities was nearly 4 times larger than credit to the fisheries and nearly 13 times more for short-term credit. These magnitudes reflect differences in the nature of these two economic activities and in their respective development stage (see Table 2-14 and Figure 2-2).

Extension and Technical Assistance

2.72

Extension and technical assistance are executed by EMATER-PI which has staff located in Parnaíba and Luís Correia since 1976. During the period 1976-80, 52 fishermen received some type of technical assistance in fishing technology, fish marketing and organization.

2.73

The extension system is geared to assist the fishing family as a

whole; consequently, the women of the house and the children also receive some type of assistance in the form of nutrition, hygiene, health and education. During 1976-80, 184 fishing families were assisted through such programs. Today there are seven groups of housewives, of which five are actively organized and two are in an earlier stage of organization.

2.74

As presented in Table 2-15, financial resources applied in the area of fisheries extension and technical assistance have increased steadily since 1975. On a per family basis, financial resources, in real terms, have not increased since 1978 when they were US\$23.8.

Table 2-14: CREDIT OPERATIONS IN FISHERIES - BANCO DO BRASIL

Credit	1977		1978		1979		1980 ¹	
	No.	Cr\$	No.	Cr\$	No.	Cr\$	No.	Cr\$
Long-term (Investimento)	8	78	8	304.3	44	2638	68	6813
Short-term (Custeio)	10	81.2	26	479.2	10	156.9	30	1574
TOTAL	18	159.2	34	783.5	54	2794.9	98	8387

¹For the same period (Jan-Aug 1980) and for the same municipalities, credit to agriculture were 255 long-term loans (Cx\$28,789) and 375 short-term loans (Cz\$46,753).

2.75

The extension system has had an impact in the area, particularly on: (a) adoption of new fishing technologies and (b) assessment and execution of nonfishing activities. In the area of technology

adoption, the extension system has been instrumental in introducing the few existing motorized boats and in assisting the fishermen in the operation and maintenance of their vessels. In the area of nonfishing activities, the extension system, through their social workers, has emphasized income-earning activities that are carried out by the other family members, particularly women. For example, the extension system has assisted these families in making full use of existing (in some areas rather poor) agricultural resources. This includes several uses of babassu nuts, cashew nuts and several other trees; the development of horticulture; and the fabrication of 'artisanal products

Figure 2-2: BANCO DO BRASIL - NUMBER OF LOANS (1977-80)

Table 2-15: TECHNICAL ASSISTANCE - FUNDS ALLOCATION TO THE FISHERIES (in Cr\$)

Sources of Funds	Years				
	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979
EMBATER/SUDEPE	271000	618000	801000	1066756	1244978
SENAR	-	-	-	117819	219062
TOTAL	271000	618000	801000	1184575	1464040
in US\$ of each year ¹	33341	57296	56655	64671	53081

¹The Average Exchange rates were:

	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979
US\$1.00 = Cr\$	8128	10786	14138	18371	27581

For October 1980, US\$1.00 =Cr\$ 57.90.

(eog., carpets, clothes),. These income-earning activities are particularly important during the off-harvesting season (September-December).

2.76

The information available from each annual yearbook is not sufficient to be able to assess EMATER's performance in the fishery sector. The data available today and the way they are collected are incomplete. In particular, one could cite number of courses, visits, interviews and experiments; however, the effectiveness of those actions is unknown. During field visits, one could see several limiting aspects of the way those interventions are implemented: (i) in terms of the number of interventions, these were small with regard to the size of the

target group under consideration. Although one could find excellent professionals, if no additional resources are allocated, the rate of effective coverage will be very small; (ii) in terms of quality of the programs, some of them have been particularly appealing to the fishing family, i.e., food production and fishing equipment and technology; (iii) in terms of training needs, it was felt that much more training should be given to the local staff--several courses have been given with no systematic training to the EMATER staff in charge of them; (iv) in terms of preferences, additional effort will have to be made to capture individual people's preferences--further fishermen participation is needed; (v) in terms of planning at the local level, the fisheries team needs more autonomy and funds--whenever conflicts arise resulting from the use of facilities and equipment (e.g., cars), there is a bias in favor of agriculture extension activities; and (vi) in terms of demands, the fishermen and their families are clearly demanding more technical assistance and training, most of which cannot be provided now.

2.77

Finally, it is important to mention that there are other channels providing technical assistance to fishermen, all of them with

the participation of EMATER's technicians. The most important of those channels is the Port Authority/Navy that offers once or twice a year (depending on demand) courses in navigation, safety and resource management.

III. LONG-TERM DEVELOPMENT OPTIONS AND STRATEGY

Large- and Small-Scale Fisheries

3.1

The major contribution of fisheries to development comes through the generation of higher income levels, the production of food and the creation of productive employment. Consequently, two of the basic goals of fishery sector policy is to improve the welfare of low-income fishing families by increasing their productivity and to meet domestic needs by supplying larger amounts of relatively cheap animal protein to low-income consumers in both rural and urban areas.

3.2

In accomplishing these goals one must place a major emphasis on the development of small-scale fisheries (SSF) in rural areas.

The economic and social development of SSF has become a major concern in Brazil today. SSF can contribute to both a fuller and, sometimes, more economical utilization of existing resources and to an increased productivity of a population that has fishing as its only or main source of income and welfare.

3.3

This is not to say, however, that large-scale fisheries (LSF) are not important within the Brazilian context, but they are of lesser importance when enhancing rural development. Most LSF are organized like other enterprises in the agroindustrial sector, and where their activities are vertically integrated with the processing sector, these activities are mostly detached from the rural sector and are not family-oriented enterprises (with regard to the fishermen involved). The major differences between LSF and SSF concern (a) the type of organizational structure, (b) the scale of harvesting and processing operation, (c) the ability to reach large export markets, and (d) the degree of mechanization achieved in vessels and gear operation.

3.4

In several respects, LSF and SSF are complementary in nature.

For example, (a) where LSF are developed, other forms of fisheries may find access to expanded and more concentrated local and foreign markets; (b) as LSF demand large and fairly sophisticated shore facilities, these facilities can be used by SSF, on a complementary basis, especially where proper design allows for this; and (c) where SSF are devoted solely to the exploitation of resources near the coast, large-scale fishing can exploit the deep-sea fish stocks farther out. However, the unplanned development of one or other type of fisheries may result in significant sources of conflict. Such conflict arises when both types of enterprise compete for the same fishing grounds or the same domestic market.

3.5

In formulating options for the development of fisheries, an assessment must be made of the technological pathways that are to be followed and of the strategies required to move along these pathways with minimal disruptions of institutional arrangements and fishermen's incomes. This section will put some emphasis on analyzing the scope and prospects for LSF, the top level of that technological path.

3.6

For SSF in Brazil there is generally good scope for development, particularly in the Northeast, due to the existence of rich fish resources in coastal areas. The total catch can be increased by motorizing boats and by better use of fishing methods. There is an even greater scope for the reduction of postharvest losses. Such improvements will benefit most fishermen, as well as other associated with the industry. This has proven to be especially true where a program includes improved processing at the village level. There is also scope for improvements in handling, infrastructure, roads, vehicles, marketing and distribution. It is also important to note that the economy of large vessels has been affected by the relatively high cost of energy. Studies have shown that deep-sea fishing consumes five to ten times more energy per calorie output than coastal fishing. Within the harvesting sector, energy usage depends upon the size of the vessels, their tonnage, the technology used, and the efficiency in fishing and fishing methods. To make up for such cost increases, LSF are motivated to catch high-value species to satisfy high-income markets, particularly exports. Consequently, it would be at the advantage of the country, particularly to low-income consumers in rural and urban areas, to develop the SSF further.

Elements for Project Design

3.7

In developing an individual fishery, a balance needs to be ascertained among the various stages of such activities as catching, processing and marketing. To ensure the productivity of the fishing effort proposed and to sustain production over time, fisheries projects should emphasize resource management, including stock assessment, fishery policies, and creation and maintenance of surveillance systems. Also, projects in this area should endeavor to assist in minimizing losses by introducing sanitation methods and low-cost technologies for the handling of fish in the boat, during landing, in processing at the village level, and in the subsequent marketing and distribution. Prevention of food losses will also demand physical investment in refrigeration and processing plants as well as Other infrastructure such as water supply and landing facilities.

3.8

The establishment of adequate marketing and distribution systems to reach rural and urban consumers is essential. In addition, the strategy would be incomplete if institutional

development is not considered in its totality. This includes the allocation of funds to the systems of research, training, education and extension.

3.9

An important element of a long-term development strategy is technology. Often development through rationalization--or increasing the productivity of existing methods of production--is preferable to modernization. This is important since due to cultural, social and institutional factors, it may take considerable time before new methods are assimilated by the fishing community. By increasing the productivity of existing methods, SSF projects will maximize the social value of those activities carried out at the village level, i.e., providing employment and income to as many villages as possible. This technology must be simple and usable, and should maximize net revenues for the fishing communities while minimizing service activities that exert control over fishing income flow. The major emphasis should therefore be on the transfer and application of already existing technology.

3.10

Finally, it is important to consider programs that may be horizontally integrated with other activities carried out in rural areas. The horizontal integration will avoid overexploitation of fish resources in the long term.

Rural Transformations

3.11

It is difficult to predict the time it will take for a very underdeveloped fishery to move to higher levels of the technological path. Nor is it possible to outline with certainty all the factors which will be responsible for a change in the rate at which transformation will take place. However, several important elements must be outlined and discussed.

3.12

First, the rate of urbanization will play an important role in fishery development. Available statistics for Piauí show that population growth in urban centers will be much higher than in rural areas. Marketing, therefore, will tend to lean toward satisfying that demand; usually a demand for fresh fish. Consequently, in the long term, one will see that the proportion of fresh fish sold

will be higher than of salted and dried fish. In addition to this, in order to absorb the demand for fresh fish, market and fish preservation facilities (cold storage, ice, transport) will play a very important role.

3.13

Second, the nature of extension and training is expected to change, as different fishermen groups advance to different levels of the aforementioned technological path. While the emphasis today is much more on subsistence and in keeping a balance with regard to fishermen's participation, tomorrow's problems will be more related to keeping a real balance across a large array of economic activities.

3.14

Third, the rate at which income and income distribution is expected to change may decrease over time. Income and income distribution are expected to improve in the next ten years because of drastic changes in ownership patterns. As explained later on, fishermen's access to fishing gear and to an increased number of vessels are the factors responsible for such a change. In the long term, changes in capital-labor ratios,

due to technological change and to biological sustainability of the resource, may tend, again, to concentrate incomes although the disparity across income groups should be smaller. The concentration of capital can be avoided through appropriate regulation.

3.15

Fourth, the catch portfolio will change due to changes in prices, cost of production, and availability of existing resource. To maximize the value added gained by the individual fisherman, in the long term, from producing second- and third-class fish, new markets have to be opened and new processing methods (e.g., fish meal, salting) should be introduced. Also, the achieved improvements in fishing methods and in stock assessment research and information will discover new resources that will be at the disposal of fishermen. These fishermen will tend to adopt those new production patterns and advance even further to other levels of the technological path.

3.16

Fifth, as demand for fresh products increases, processing at the village level, though it may maintain present levels, will decrease

in importance. The potential loss in income is expected to be compensated by induced employment in other activities, within or outside the fishing villages. However, it is not clear how this activity will evolve, since its growth rate depends mainly on the rural market for salted and dried fish products.

3.17

Sixth, the village life-style is expected to change. Fish is a perishable commodity, and as fisheries produce more fresh fish, more cash will be channeled into the fishing village. These changes will transform the present, subsistence-oriented life-style at the village level. To avoid unnecessary strain on social institutions, improvements in village organization is extremely important; in practical terms, such cohesive organization should develop adequate mechanisms for reinvesting the flow of wealth into the village. This reinvestment process should consider programs for improving present housing, sanitation, health and education conditions, as well as the conditions of other social services.

3.18

Finally, the privatization of the economy is inevitable;

entrepreneurial capacity will be developed, villages will be more influenced by the growth of adjacent urban centers; isolation of fishing villages will disappear as tourism and other activities develop. However, if land tenure arrangements are beneficial to the fishermen, growth is materialized at the fishing village level, and other fishing families' activities are enhanced, it is expected that very positive long-term conditions will prevail in those fishing villages.

3.19

To achieve the abovementioned goals, the development of the fishery sector in Piauí has to consider lifting several important constraints. Part IV outlines these constraints.

IV. THE PROJECT

Objectives

4.1

Although Piauí's coastal line is short, the project represents an important step forward within the Northeast development strategy. Consequently, in accordance with the long-term development objectives and strategy presented in Section

III, the main objectives of this project are: (a) to increase the income of the fishing family in the State of Piauí and (b) to increase the amount of animal protein available to low-income consumers both in urban and rural areas. In addition, there are thousands of fishermen and several hundreds of fishing villages on the Brazilian coast who tend to benefit from this project (The project is innovative since it suggests a technology which makes a maximum use of wind power and Animizes the use of petrochemical products (i.e., diesel). The project proposes technologies which are already in use and tries to increase the productivity of the corresponding unproductive-components. The experience with this project will make artisanal fisheries development more replicable in other states, and will tend to keep a more appropriate balance between industrial fisheries and artisanal fisheries in the country).

Development Constraints

4.2

The artisanal fisheries in Piauí are facing several development constraints, the most important of all being production, organizational and marketing constraints. In addition to these main constraints, the sector faces problems in the area of

shipbuilding, extension, processing and land tenure. All these constraints are interrelated; for example, there are organizational problems that affect marketing, and there are marketing problems that affect production. However, for expository purposes, these constraints will be presented separately.

4.3

Production. First, there are too many fishermen and too few boats. Consequently, the amount of production per fisherman due to the number of effective fishing days is very low. This phenomenon has seriously constrained fishermen's income. Second, the quality of the existing amount of fishing effort is poor; some traditional vessels are poorly designed, limiting the number of fishing days per boat (the traditional sailboat cannot fish during windy days, i.e., September-December). Third, the productivity and availability of fishing gear is such that few fishermen own some, and those who do use them with very low productivity. Overall, there are other compounding factors that affect the rapid and sustained growth in production (e.g., lack of credit).

4.4

Organization. Fishermen are not well organized in the area. The lack of adequate organization has affected the institutional performance of several sectors like input supply (e.g., ice), marketing (e.g., expansion of marketing channels) and technical assistance. As stated earlier in Part II, there is only one cooperative that groups less than 5% of the total number of fishermen. There are several aspects that contribute to such problems, namely, the lack of infrastructure, within the cooperative, to supply the services that individual agents are providing at present (e.g., ice production) and the lack of working capital (very low purchasing power).

4.5

Marketing, When considering the physical aspects of marketing, the area lacks access roads and where these roads exist, they need very important improvements. In addition, transport infrastructure is not adequate, and there is a need for refrigerated trucks and other modes of transport. Also, the cold storage capacity in the coastal area is nil, although this capacity will be improved by the existing POLONORDESTE project (see para. 2.21). The existing marketing infrastructure is not large enough

to reach retail consumption centers, particularly Teresina, Piripiri and Parnaíba--this expansion will enable the gaining of additional economies of scale in marketing.

4.6

Shipbuilding. Although the area has several shipbuilders, these people have serious problems with improving their existing tools. Increase in demand for fishing vessels will require improvements in productivity. The provision of improved tools is thought to relax such constraints, minimizing potential adverse effects on employment.

4.7

Extension, training and technical assistance. The existing system for extension, training and technical assistance needs improvements and expansion. Existing information systems are inadequate to cope with an increase in the execution of existing programs. What is actually collected is of little use and certainly does not offer an appropriate framework either for monitoring or for evaluation. In addition, fisherman training programs lack appropriate equipment and vessels; in making these vessels available for training purposes, they can also be used to improve

the knowledge about existing fish resources in the area.

4.8

Processing. The quality of fish preservation methods are unsatisfactory. Losses occur (particularly in quality) due to inadequate methods for fish handling and to the lack of inputs, particularly ice. In addition, several low-quality fish (part of “second class” and all “third class” fish) could be utilized differently, thereby increasing their total intrinsic Value (e.g., smoked fish, fish meal). The system does not have such a processing capacity. The provision of such facilities, are also expected to have important price stabilization effects.

4.9

The processing of shrimp and mangrove crab are carried out at the local level by family enterprises; these units need to buy better tools and equipment, and with it improve the existing technologies. As expressed earlier, processing at the local level might change in the long term.

4.10

Land tenure. Land in the project area (fishing villages) is not

owned by the fishermen, constraining them from improving their houses and expanding the level and quality of their existing infrastructure (e.g., water supply, electricity). In addition, the lack of land ownership represents a permanent threat to the fishermen--signs of land speculation (for tourism and vacationing) is taking place, these may easily push the fishermen out of their villages.

Project Rationale: Strategy

4.11

The core of this project's strategy will be to lift most of the constraints analyzed in the last section. However, the way in which this project is expected to lift those constraints will respect several important principles. First, self-reliance, where a major emphasis will be given to fishermen's organizations, i.e., improvement of the coop, and an important infusion of training and technical assistance in the ownership and management of all available resources. The project introduces different levels of technologies for adoption. The progressive adoption of different technological levels--having gear, traditional sailboat, improved sailboat and sail/motorized boat--is expected to be incremental; that is, those who neither own boat nor gear are expected to acquire gear, those who own gear are expected to own boats,

and so on. In order to achieve self-reliance, the major emphasis of the project will be on the fishing family as the productive unit. Elements will be provided (i.e., transfer of land) to enable the fishing family to spend the expected incremental income within the fishing village level. This investment process should generate more income and employment, particularly within the set of ancillary industries.

4.12

Second, improve income distribution. This is expected to be accomplished by maximizing employment and changing the system of access to new technology. The maximization of employment is expected to be achieved by increasing the number of boats allowing fishermen to increase the number of fishing days; by improving, rather than eliminating, the processing activities carried out at the fishing village level; and by improving the local shipbuilding, net making, and boat repair activities. The system of access to technology is expected to be achieved by introducing improved sailboats and some motorized boats; they have higher productivity than traditional canoes and sailboats. Moreover, those fishermen employed on canoes, traditional sailboats and improved sailboats will have

access to credit for purchasing fishing gear (e.g., nets, hooks, line), that will enable them to share a higher proportion of future proceeds from fishing.

4.13

Third, resource conservation and management. The project is expected to improve the knowledge about existing fish resources in Piauí coastal areas. Also, technical assistance and training will be provided to test and control the productivity of available fishing gear. In addition, to avoid future (since they do not exist today) pressure over existing fish resources, the project will try to decrease fishermen's high rate of social time preference mostly due to their low income levels. The change in time preferences will be done using all previously mentioned elements plus minimizing harvesting losses and improving other sources of income (e.g., agriculture, artisanal products). In other words, to increase the degree of horizontal integration between fishing as one source of income and other sources of income available to the fishing family.

4.14

Fourth, development through rationalization rather than

modernization. This principle will be applied by introducing already known technologies and by not altering existing institutional arrangements and methods in other subsystems (e.g., marketing, processing).

4.15

Finally, institutional development. Development will not only result from increased investment but also from improving the management of market (e.g., process) and nonmarket institutions (e.g., property rights) - the cooperative will play the most important role in this area. To avoid unnecessary strain on existing institutions, the 'project has an implicitly long gestation period, e.g., few vessels are constructed in the first two years.

Project Components¹

4.16

To achieve the previously stated objectives and strategy, this project will provide:

(a) Credit to fishermen for fishing vessels including 40 canoes, 31 traditional sailboats, 114 improved sailboats, and 47 motorized

¹ When referring to credit, the text is quoting total credit and not incremental credit requirements. Credit terms and conditions for each component are outlined in para. 5.4.

sailboats. This also includes engine and safety equipment;

(b) credit to fishermen for purchasing several types of fishing gear. e.g., gillnets, cast nets;

(c) credit to merchants, shrimp and mangrove crab processors, and shipbuilders for equipment and working capital;

(d) credit to the fishermen's coop for equipment and working capital;

(e) funds ("Fondo Perdido") for extension, technical assistance (including marketing), experiment and research; and

(f) funds for consulting purposes and administration.

Fishing Vessels Safety Equipment and Fishing Gear

4.17

The project will provide credit to fishermen for the purchase of about 185 nonmotorized vessels and 47 motorized vessels for the purpose of expanding the quantity and improving the quality

of the existing fishing effort For the total of 185 nonmotorized vessels, the project is expected to finance 40 canoes, 31 traditional sailing vessels and 114 improved sailing vessels. The improvement i boat design will be achieved by introducing a centered-board type whaleboat, so called because this type of boats was used many years ago in the Arctic, Antarctic and other oceans in the capture of whales. This vessel is easily beached because the centered board folds up inside a box, and the mast is stepped and stayed each time, just as in the present case. The improved stability of the boat will increase the number of fishing days. Also, this type of boat can be motorized with little modification. The total cost of this component is approximately Cz\$47.3 million. These cost estimates include 196 sets of safety equipment (Ct\$4.9 million), namely, fire extinguishers, life jackets, life rings, flares, mining lights, horn, emergency rations and water, and the like.

4.18

The project will also provide credit to fishermen for purchasing different types of gear, particularly cast nets and gillnets. Most gear proposed will be supplied in response to the overall incremental investment. The total cost of this subcomponent is

estimated at Cr\$89.7 million.

Marketing, Processing and Shipbuilding

4.19

Credit will be made available to small merchants who need working capital or some small investment in transport. The cost of this component amounts only to Cr\$4 million). Also, credit will be available for those fishing families who process shrimp and mangrove crab; this will include tables, utensils and working capital (like seasonal credit) and to buy certain inputs (e.g., salt, fuelwood). The credit allocated to these items is expected to amount to Cr\$10 million. Finally, a line of credit will be open to benefit shipbuilders, particularly the first and second years of the project, to purchase tools and equipment. The total credit for shipbuilders is estimated at C4)4.5 million.

The Cooperative of Luis Correia

4.20

The fishermen's coop will receive credit for investments as well as for working capital (capital de giro). The major investments will include transport (i.e., trucks) and equipment for salting and

smoking fish, processing mangrove crab, fish meal equipment, ice plant, and equipment needed in the retail market place, For a 5-year period, this credit will amount to Cr\$21.4 million.

4.21

In order to create stronger purchasing power and relax present working capital constraints, credit will be available to the coop for those purposes (capital de giro). The need for such working capital has been estimated at Cx\$12.5 million for 5 years.

4.22

The coop will also receive grant funds for other purposes (see para. 4.26), which are outlined below.

Exteision and Technical Assistance

4.23

Extension and technical assistance are one of the most important components of this project. The objective here is to provide the necessary personnel and the equipment to transfer technologies related to those income generating activities to the fishing family. Certainly, extension and training of the fishermen will be of vital importance; however, the training of other family members

in net making and repair, fish conservation and nutrition, as well as production of food and artisanal products will also play an important role. This component includes funds to hire the necessary staff, particularly social workers and fishing engineers (at the technical level), material and equipment, and the payment of services. The cost of this component is expected to be Cr\$98.5 million. These costs include a small revolving fund for the women groups (called “Fondo Comunitario”), which amounts to Cx\$560 thousand.

4.24

During the first year of the project, it is expected that extension and technical assistance will be given to 346 fishermen in those aspects related to fishing technology, marketing, preservation, and cooperative principles. The extension system will also give credit assistance to more or less 198 fishermen. In addition, 80 families will be trained in net making, artisanal products, health and hygiene, and first aid. The fishermen in these 80 families will be trained in the use of motorized vessels or gear; particularly fishing technology, maintenance of bicycles (for line fishing), use and maintenance of safety equipment, and engine repair and maintenance.

4.25

The technical assistance will also be extended to shipbuilders--to improve boat design--and to those fishing families processing shrimp and mangrove crab.

4.26

Furthermore, technical assistance will be given to the Cooperative of Luis Correia in two forms. First, it is expected that POLONORDESTE, during the first year of the project, will continue to fund the administrative personnel of the coop including the already hired fishing engineer. This item will amount to Cz\$1.5 million. Second, OCEPI will provide technical assistance in administration, auditing, accounting and marketing to the coop during the five years of the project. This assistance; amounting to Cr\$3.5 million, includes a vehicle, services, expenses and personnel.

Experiment and Research

4.27

The adoption of new technology as well as increases in the size of the existing fishing effort will demand careful experiment and research. The experimental component will be mostly

on fishing gear and equipment jointly with different types of fishing systems. Existing sets of gear are not always adequate to maximize the sustained rent from the existing fish resources.

4.28

Also, there is a need to improve existing knowledge about fish resources available in Piauí's coastal waters. For this purpose, personnel as well as equipment (including a small fishing vessel) have been included in this project.

4.29

The output expected for the first year of the project includes tests with different types of fishing gear, testing different horizontal and vertical positions, and determining a productivity framework for different species, e.g., sea bass, king mackerel, mackerel, catfish, tarpon and camurim (centropomus).

4.30

The total cost of these items adds up to Cr\$22.2 million.

Consulting

4.31

The project includes consulting for fish stock assessment in the Piauí coastal zone, for marketing studies (consumption and distribution), for experimenting with different types of fishing gear, for improving the evaluation system of extension and training, and for shipbuilding. The project will finance a total of 32 man-months of consulting, of which 15 man-months are expected to be used during the first year of the project (i.e., 5 man-months for shipbuilding, 3 man-months for marketing, 3 for stock assessment, 2 for extension and 2 for experiment). The total cost of this component is nearly Cr\$20 million. A detailed analysis of tasks and a timetable (including terms of reference) are presented in Annex II.

V. PROJECT COSTS AND FINANCING

Cost Estimates¹

5.1

Total project cost is estimated at C4 341.6 million (US\$6.1 million; US\$1 = Cr\$56). Cost estimates are presented in Table

¹ As the project follows the normal review process, this estimate may have to be revised,

5-1 (for additional details, see Annex VII); these estimates are only base costs, since they do not include price or physical contingencies and exclude taxes and duties. The estimates are based on September 1980 prices.

Project Implementation

5.2

The project would be implemented over a period of five years from 1981 through 1986. The implementation schedule for different activities is presented in Table 5-2. Most project items are spread over the entire project period. Given the nature of this project, evaluation will take place at the end of the second year, and a redefinition of project activities, based on effective progress, may take place.

Lending Terms and Conditions

5.3

To avoid concentration of capital, those fishermen who already possess a motorized vessel will not be allowed to use project credit funds to purchase additional motorized boats made available by the project or, for that matter, other types of vessels

too. Those who possess sailboats will be able to buy improved sailboats or motorized boats. For those purchases, the amount of money received from the sale of the old vessel will be used as down payment (fisherman's equity).

5.4

The credit terms used here will be the same terms stipulated in the Rural Credit Manual for those funds coming from the POLONORDESTE Program. For long-term investment such as equipment for the cooperative, the manual allows repayment in 12 years, with 5 years grace. For vessels, seasonal credit and working capital (capital de giro), a repayment of 8 years with 2 years grace, 2 years with no grace, and 120 days is allowed, respectively.

5.5

Since the value of motorized vessels is higher than the POLONORDESTE limit of 100 VRs, these vessels will be financed through the cooperative. A Bank loan, i.e., BNGC, could go up to 7,500 MVRs if it is for the cooperative. A purchase agreement between the coop and the interested fisherman will be signed to transfer ownership--in proportion to repayment--to the final

Table 5-1: TOTAL PROJECT COSTS (in '000 1980 Cr\$)¹

Items		Year	I	II	III	IV	V	VI
I	Credit ²							
	A. To Fishermen							
			5630	6847.5	8960	11930	13827	47265
	Vessels							
	Gear		10461	10794.5	17583	22811.5	28046.8	89696.8
	B. To Merchants, Processors and Shipbuilders		5800	4300	2800	2800	2800	18500
	To Cooperative							
			8371	4200	4921	3700	250	21441.9
	Equipment							
	Working Capital		2500	2500	2500	2500	2500	12500
II	Funds (Fondo Perdido)							
	A. Extension/Technical Assistance		12721.8	20140.6	20936	22485.3	22163.3	98447
	B. Research/Experiment		5000	3750	3750	3750	3750	20000
	C. Experiment Unit		2200	-	-	-	-	2200
	D. Consulting		9288	4456.8	2313.4	1939.2	1939.2	19936.6
	E. Project Administration		1328.2	1328.2	1328.2	1328.2	1328.2	6640.8
	F. Coop, Administration		1509.3	-	-	-	-	1509.3
	G. OCEPI's Technical Assistance to Coop		1050	600	600	600	600	3450
	TOTAL		65859.3	58917.6	65691.6	73844.2	77204.5	341587.4

¹Detailed cost estimates are presented in Annex VII, Table 1.

²This is total credit. Figures on incremental credit are provided in Annex VII, Table 2.

user. The guarantor of such a loan will be the coop which has sufficient fixed assets to offer as collateral.

Table 5-2: CRONOGRAM

Items		Years				
		I	II	III	IV	V
1	Canoas a Remo	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----
2	Canoas a Vela (V ₁)	-----				
3	Canoas a Vela (V ₂)	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----
4	Barcos a Motor (M ₁)	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----
5	Equipamentos Seguranca	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----
6	Tarrafas	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----
7	Pontas de Redes	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----
8	Pargueiras	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----
9	Unidad de Processamento de Peixes	-----				
10	Unidad de Frio	-----				
11	Unidad de Salga	-----				
12	Unidad de Farinha	-----				
13	Unidad de Defumaçao	-----				
14	Proces de Carauguejo		-----			
15	Vehiculos Pesados	-----	-----	-----	-----	
16	Vehiculos Leves	-----			-----	
17	Postos de Venda	-----		-----		-----
18	Credito Comerciantes	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----
19	Credito Processamento Caranguejo	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----
20	Credito Processamento Camarao	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----
21	Credito Constr. Navais	-----	-----			
22	Capital Giro COPELCO	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----
23	Ext. Ass. Tecnica	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----
24	Pesquisa-Experimentaçao	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----
25	Unidad Demostrativa	-----				
26	Consultoria Comerciantes	-----	-----			

5.6

Since the value of motorized vessels is higher than the POLONORDESTE limit of 100 MVRs, these vessels will be financed through the cooperative. A Bank loan, i.e., BNCC, could

go up to 7,500 MVRs if it is for the cooperative. A purchase agreement between the coop and the interested fisherman will be signed to transfer ownership--in proportion to repayment-to the final user. The guarantor of such a loan will be the coop which has sufficient fixed assets to offer as collateral.

5.7

The auditing of such loans will be done by the banks to make sure that terms and conditions as well as objectives are met through the credit program.

VI. ORGANIZATION AND MANAGEMENT

Organization

6.1

The purpose of this section is to outline the organizational arrangement of those aspects specifically related to the fisheries component. As in the case of the marketing component, an agency, in this case SUDEPE, has been assigned the planning, coordinating and minor execution (i.e., research, experiment, enforcement and policy) of the fisheries component. For this purpose, SUDEPE will allocate in its Piauí regional office additional

staff (two technical experts, plus administrative personnel), at SUDEPE's expense, to carry out the abovementioned functions (see Table 6-1).

6.2

Besides the banking system, which in a way will execute the credit component (i.e., Banco do Brasil, Banco do Estado do Piani, Banco do Nordeste and Banco Nacional do Credito Cooperativo), two agencies will be responsible for the execution of the project, namely, MIATER and OCEPI (for a description of MIATER, see the working paper on Agricultural Extension; and for a description of OCEPI, see the working paper on Marketing).

6.3

EMATER will execute the extension, training and credit assistance for the overall project. For this purpose, an organizational structure has been set up in Teresina (the state's regional office), whereby EMATER will have a project manager with two advisers (one in social work, the other in fisheries). This central unit will be extended to two offices at the local level where the necessary personnel and equipment are provided for the project. The extension and credit assistance work will be carried out in

the ten fishing villages grouped in five subgroups defined in terms of quality of access roads and transport, and demographical concentration (for details, see Annex IV). A total of 11 teams--each team is formed by I social worker and I fishery technician--are proposed to cover the following fishing villages: (a) Barra Grande, Macapa and Barrinha--3 teams; (b) Borda Mariana--2 teams; (c) Pedra do Sal and Catandugas--1 team; (d) Cajuero--2 teams; and (e) Coqueiro, Carnanbinha and Luis Correia--3 teams (detailed terms of reference are presented in Annex IV).

6.4

OCEPI will provide technical assistance in management, accounting, auditing and legal aspects of cooperative development. The project provides the necessary resources to OCEPI, enough to visit the cooperative once a week. The execution of this component is a key to project success.

6.5

Other agencies like CEPA, FAD and/or private consulting firms will be responsible for the execution of the consulting work in the area of fish stock assessment (FAO), marketing (CEPA), experiment (FAO), and extension (consulting firm or PAO).

Table 6-1: IMPLEMENTATION

Ações	Instituições												
	SEC. PLAN.	EMATER	SUDEPE	SUDEPE-PNP	SUDENE	FAO-WECAF	BB	BNB	BEP	BNCC	CAPITANIA	OCEPI	SPU
Planejamento	o	v	v	v	v	v							
Extensao		x											
Ass. Tecnica/Pescadores		x											
Ass. Tecnica Coop		x											
Ass. Tecnica Projecto					x								
Credito Pescadores							x	x	x				
Credito Comerciantes							x	x	x				
Credito Processadores							x	x	x				
Credito Cooperativa							x	x	x	x			
Credito Const. Navais							x	x	x				
Ass. Tecnica Const. Navais		x											
Ass. Tecnica Processadores		x											
Trenamiento Percadores		x											
Politica Pesqueira			x										
Fiscalizacao Pesca			x										
Registro Gral Pesca			x										
Monitoria/Evaluacion						x							
Ass. Gerencial Coop												x	
Ass. Juridica Coop												x	
Ass. Contable Coop												x	
Pesquisa-Experimentacao				x	x								
Control Estad. Pesca				x									
Regularizacao Terra													
Registro Profs. Pescad.											x		x

o = coordinação

v = correspondência

x = execução

6.6

The organigram for this component, presented in Figure 6-1, is rather simple.

Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E)¹

6.7

Present fisheries informational systems are rather weak in the State of Piauí. Two main sources of information exist at the state level: SUDEPE-PDP and EMATER. SUDEPE-PDP collects information on landings and prices in some fishing villages in the project area. Although the data available are useful, they need more improvement. EMATER has an information system where the data is generated from the “bottom up”; the extension agent reports to the local office, this office reports to the

¹ Specific details on the M&E framework proposed is presented in Annex V.

state office, and the state office reports to EflBRATER and POLONORDESTE. Data on the number of families visited, the type of visit (formal or informal), the topic conveyed during the visit are some of the information collected by EMATER. When it comes to aggregate these data, however, the system fails to feed management with the type of information required for improvement in management and for the evaluation of the extension and training system used. A sample of Information Sheets used by EMATER is presented in Annex VI.

6.8

Information on prices, quantities, efficiency in use of investments, performance indicator for the executing agencies, fishing family members participation, impacts on consumption and income have to be clearly studied as part of the overall M&E effort.

6.9

In reporting the progress of this project to management, information about credit for vessels, gear, working capital and equipment should be monitored. Also, the system should report on progress achieved by extension, training, experiment and consulting. The system should be simple and easy to maintain.

6.10

The system should also consider the collection of relevant information for periodic evaluation of the project. These evaluations have to be done in terms of the effective contributions of means (project components) to the specified project objectives. In this case, two overall objectives have been specified: (a) improve the fisherman family's standard of living, and (b) improve the consumption of animal protein by low-income groups in the state and perhaps in other neighboring states (i.e., Maranhao and Ceara). Consequently, the main objective of this process will be to evaluate the extent to which each of the project components are contributing to those objectives. The system that will be proposed here should be easy to execute.

6.11

The responsibilities for M&E should be centralized by the Project Unit. For the purpose of better coordination and execution of such M&E process, the Project Unit should coordinate very closely with SUDEPE. The M&E unit for the project should, if necessary, carry out a baseline survey which will serve as a benchmark for future comparisons of performance. This survey should only

collect data relevant to feed into the analytic framework for the monitoring and evaluation of the project proposed in Annex V.

6.12

Assurances will be obtained during negotiations that the Project Unit will prepare quarterly reports and an annual summary covering the fisheries component. Quarterly reports should reach the Bank within six weeks of the end of each calendar quarter, and the annual summary within six weeks of the end of the reporting year.

VII. FINANCIAL AND ECONOMIC ANALYSIS

Changes in Project Design

7.1

Two major changes have taken place in project design: (a) downsizing of the quantity of fishing effort, and (b) redesign of the Extension and Technical Assistance component.

7.2

The preparation report proposed to finance 44 canoes, 31 sailboats, 154 improved sailboats, 47 traditional motorized

boats, 31 improved motorized boats, and 263 sets of safety equipment. The level of fishing effort was reduced to 40 canoes, 31 sailboats, 114 improved sailboats, 47 traditional motorized vessels, no improved motorized vessels, and only 196 sets of safety equipment. Several multicriteria were used in decreasing the size of the fishing effort, namely, (a) POLONORDESTE threshold income level their funds are to benefit people whose income is less than 200 M.VRs; (b) effective employment and income distribution impact; and (c) capacity of the ancillary industries (e.g., shipbuilding) in supplying the necessary services to the project.

7.3

The original design of the extension and technical assistance services was based on a ratio of extensionists to fishermen (1 extensionist per 80 fishermen). This ratio overestimates the need for extensionists, given the quality of the access to fishing villages (e.g., road, transport) and the geographical concentration of fishermen in any given area. The proposed 14 teams (with all the costs and expenses these require) were reduced to 11, and the creation of these teams will be done frequently as the project needs them.

Illustrative Boat Models

7.4

To rationalize the overall development within the sector and, progressively, benefit the largest number of fishing families, several technological options are offered by the project. All these options are well known in the area, even motorized vessels (with a combination of engine and sail). For the purposes of the financial analysis, one can divide fishermen in two groups, those who fish at sea and those who are sole operators and mangrove crab fishermen.

7.5

Among those who fish at sea, one can classify them into TI and TP fishermen and, furthermore, each TI and TP can be divided in three groups (a) fishermen without boat and gear, (b) fishermen with gear (no boat), and (c) owners who possess both boat and gear.

7.6

The three technological levels, offered to each group of fishermen, can be identified by a simple typology defined in terms of the

type of vessels financed by the project: (i) traditional sailboat, (ii) improved sailboat, and (iii) motorized boat. As is shown in Figure 7-1, without the project, the improved sailboat technology does not exist. The improvements in quantity and quality of the fishing effort (including both boat and gear) will cause 247 TP fishermen to become TI fishermen. Such a small number could come from those who do not have gear (150) and from those who possess some type of gear (454). It is expected that the majority, if not all, of fishermen without gear will become part of the TI group, including some who possess gear.

7.7

Motorized vessels are increased from 24 to 71; the 47 boats that are financed by the project are expected to be purchased by owners of traditional sailboats. Traditional sailboats (31 in total) are expected to be purchased by fishermen with or without gear. Improved sailboats (114) are expected to be purchased by owners of traditional sailboats (27), and fishermen who at present have gear (87).

7.8

The tables presented in Figure 7-1 do not include the other

categories of fishermen (e.g., mangrove crab fishermen); some of them might become TP coastal fishermen too. However, for cultural reasons as well as for reasons related to their involvement in other rural sector activities (i.e., agriculture), it is not expected that those fishermen will become coastal fishermen. For this type of fishermen the project is supplying 40 canoes.

Figure 7-1: PIAUÍ FISHERIES PROJECT - TECHNOLOGICAL OPTIONS

Without Project							
TI				TP			
	Traditional Sailboat	Improved Sailboat	Motorized Boat		Traditional Sailboat	Improved Sailboat	Motorized Boat
Fisherman without Gear (S/A _i)	263	X	96	S/A _i	150	X	X
Fisherman with Gear (A _i)	473	X	X	A _i	454	X	X
Boat Owners (0)	56	X	24	0	18	X	X
			= 912				= 622
With Project							
TI				TP			
	Traditional Sailboat	Improved Sailboat	Motorized Boat		Traditional Sailboat	Improved Sailboat	Motorized Boat
Fisherman without Gear (S/A _i)	X	X	284	S/A _i	X	X	X
Fisherman with Gear (A _i)	261	342	X	A _i	357	X	X
Boat Owners (0)	87	114	71	0	18	X	X
			= 1159				= 375

7.9

It is important to outline some of the main features of the boat models. While, from the viewpoint of quantity of fish production, the largest percentage is represented by second- and *third-class fish (with the exception of the motorized vessels), from viewpoint of value of production, first- and third-class fish are the most important; this is due mainly to the quantity and price structure prevailing in the area. Consequently, it is expected (as

shown in the section on sensitivity analysis) that the project's net benefits will be more sensitive to changes in the price of first- and third-class fish than to the price of second-class fish.

7.10

The structure and composition of the operation and maintenance cost (O&M) are rather interesting, since the largest proportion of those costs are represented by payments to labor (the fisherman). As a result, one would expect that the switching value (in percentage terms) of the labor cost would be much smaller than any other cost items; even in the budget of motorized vessels. However, these payments to fishermen are a rather fixed proportion of total costs and are not expected to change as a result of the project. The system for distributing the proceeds is set by tradition and culture and it is not expected to change from one day to the other. Also, because payments to labor are a large proportion of O&M costs, the value of the labor conversion factors will be an important determinant of the economic rate of return of the project.

7.11

In the case of motorized vessels (engine and sail), expenditures

on bait and repair and maintenance of the boat and gear seem to be much more important than such items as diesel, ice, and food. The cost of diesel, compared to other O&M items, is proportionally low because of the combined use of engine and sail, and the small size of the engines proposed.

7.12

Given the nature of the proposed fishing technology, the overall financial performance of these boat models depends mostly on those parameters associated with the gross and net value of production. In particular, performance depends on the value attached to the productivity of the fishing gear, the number of fishing days, the proportion shared by each class of fish, the harvesting losses coefficients (i.e. physical losses), and the level of self-consumption. Except for those parameters which depend on market forces (i.e. prices), most of the other parameters depend on the performance of the extension service: the capacity of the production system to increase its productivity over time.

7.13

The detailed information on each production model is presented in Annex VII.

Beneficiaries

7.14

The typology of production models--vessels, budgets--gave a notion of the type of project beneficiaries. However, as an important state development effort, the project would benefit directly and indirectly several segments of the population. The principal beneficiaries would be among those who are actively engaged in fish production, processing, marketing and distribution. One of the ultimate benefits of this project would however accrue to those masses of rural consumers who are expected to be provided with increased quantities of rather inexpensive animal protein of high quality. The coastal zone would benefit most from the project-induced employment and income.

7.15

The program is designed to benefit directly, with productive investments, 1,800 fishermen and indirectly, with technical assistance, extension and training, a total of 2,000 families.

7.16

The fishing family as a unit will benefit from extension and

technical assistance given to some family members, particularly to fishermen's wives. By doing so, the family income will stabilize, particularly during the off-harvesting season, and is expected to increase at all levels. This is true also for those who do not possess any gear; for them, present incomes are 3.5 MVRs per year (i.e., those working as TP fishermen) and is expected to increase substantially depending on the way they sell their labor (for details, see paras. 7.37-7.41).

Production, Marketing and Prices

7.17

The project would increase fish production in Piauí, and Northeast Brazil, through a series of interrelated improvements affecting fish catch levels, preservation, marketing and distribution. Specifically, provision of more and better fish materials and training in more sophisticated techniques should raise catch levels, improved processing would preserve fish for wider dissemination, and strengthened marketing should make it possible to retail fish throughout the Northeast. Incremental fish production is estimated at about 6.0 thousand tons (net weight) at full implementation. The value of such incremental production is a little less than \$3 million on the basis of September 1980

beach landing prices.

7.18

Fish production under the project is expected to be marketed in Piauí as well as in other parts of Northeast Brazil, particularly neighboring states. Part of the total catch will be marketed and consumed fresh, the remaining will be marketed after processing (e.g., salted, dried). The expansion and improvement of existing marketing channels will stabilize fish prices both on a seasonal basis and among various consumer groups both in urban and rural areas.

7.19

Overall consumption is expected to increase due to population and income growth. Using data collected by the ENDEP Household Survey for the Northeast, an attempt was made to estimate expenditure-income elasticities based on a cross-section of rural income groups. The ENDEF's cross-section data include nine income categories where expenditure on fish/meat (i.e., animal protein put together) was regressed against average income in each income-group category¹. This econometric relationship

¹ A double-log function was used with the following results:

$\ln E = 1.9 + 0.975x \ln Yx + 0.1D_1 - 0.85 D_2$

t prob: (0.9995) (1.000)

$R^2 = 0.9445$

$F_{3,23} = 130.5$

shows that the expenditure-income elasticity is very high (i.e., $n = 0.975$) and, consequently, increases in per capita income in the Northeast region will be accompanied by almost an equivalent increase in per capita fish consumption.

7.20

To illustrate how important the total quantity of fish supplied by the project is over the estimated total “apparent consumption,” several scenarios are presented here. These scenarios are constructed assuming the following rate of growth in population: low (1.8%), medium (2.2%) and high (4.0%). These growth rates are compared with alternative values of per capita income or, for that matter, to per capita fish consumption (which includes only sea fish consumption): low (4.9 kg/capita/year or kcy), medium (5.5 kcy) and high (6.5 kcy). The results are presented in Table 7-1. One can see from this table that even assuming very conservative growth rate in population and per capita income, the project’s supply of fish represents only a very small proportion of the total¹.

where E represents expenditures on fish and meat (fish represents 20% to 30% of the total); Y represents average income in each income category; and D1 and D2 represent two dummy variables reflecting consumption in metropolitan areas (they were not statistically significant).

¹ The comparisons between population growth and per capita fish consumption can be done because of the very high correlations between expenditure and income.

7.21

It is important to add that consumption patterns vary across income groups. Although fish consumption expenditures (i.e. in money terms) increase with income, consumption in physical terms, may stay relatively even across income groups: as per capita income goes up, people tend to eat better quality fish or change their consumption habits from smoked/salted fish to fresh fish.

Table 7-1: ESTIMATED SEAFISH CONSUMPTION FOR THE NORTHEAST, 1980-85 (in thousand tons)¹

Population Growth Rate	Per Capita Consumption (kg/yr)					
	Low (4.9)		Medium (5.5)		High (6.5)	
	1980	1985	1980	1985	1980	1985
Low (1.8)	162549	174947	182451	196372	215624	232076
Medium (2.2)	168060	183211	188639	205645	222937	243035
High (4.0)	192854	220407	216469	347396	255827	292377

¹Baseline population projections are based on IBRD Report No. 2604-BR, and baseline fish consumption projections are based on ENDEF Household Survey, 1977.

7.22

Existing price series for 1977, 1978 and 1979 (with some point estimates for 1980) show that real prices for most fish species have stayed constant despite variations in production and that, though there are price variations during the year, these variations are not very pronounced for the same fish species. The main explanation for this is the fact that the fish marketing system's

capacity to absorb excess production is very high: Piauí's products can be easily marketed outside the state, particularly in Recife and Fortaleza. For this project's economic and financial analysis, we have assumed that fish prices, in real terms, will stay constant as they have been in the past.

7.23

Specifically, for purposes of the economic and financial analysis, projections have been based on the following average beach-landing price: CF\$65 per kg of first-class fish, CR 35 per kg of second-class fish and CB\$20 per kg of third-class fish¹. Adequate preservation facilities, storage, and marketing channels, will tend to stabilize prices.

7.24

It is important that prices be monitored very carefully given the nature of fishing enterprises. For this reason, the project will assist the Brazilians to carry out a fish marketing study and will establish a monitoring and evaluation unit which is expected to collect and provide valuable price-related information to management in the project area.

¹ Historical price series show the following prices: CF\$60, CR\$40 and C1\$25 for first, second and third class of fish respectively. See the section on sensitivity analysis. Prices paid by COPELCO are even higher (see para. 2.50).

Benefits and Justification

7.25

This project is innovative in the sense of emphasizing the development of artisanal fisheries in the Northeast, providing technology which is expected to minimize the use of scarce energy resources and providing a framework for replicability in other states. The principal benefits of the project would consist of increased production and improved distribution of fish throughout Piauí and, by extension, to some neighboring states. The increased revenues from the project would principally benefit small-scale fishermen and their families. Increased production but particularly improved marketing and distribution should help to improve nutrition for the rural population, by providing a regular and relatively cheap source of protein. Additional benefits will be generated particularly in the form of extension and technical assistance to the other members of the fishing family. Also, the expansion of fish production will benefit several other economic agents (e.g., ancillary industries) through increases in income and employment.

7.26

Furthermore, as the first organized development effort ever undertaken in the State of Piauí's fishery sector, the project is also expected to benefit the sector's performance in many ways. There would be substantial improvements in the institutional support system like credit, extension, technical assistance, training and research. The sector's operational capability, such as building, repair and maintenance of traditional and improved vessels, gear, engines, would be raised to more adequate levels.

The Financial Analysis

7.27

This analysis has been carried out for each level of technology, namely, traditional sailboats, improved sailboats and motorized boats (a combination of engine and sail). Those fishermen who adopt any of these technological levels will find them very profitable, even if adoption of "inferior" technological levels are conceived, like purchasing only fishing gear.

7.28

Those who neither possess boat nor gear, could, as a first step, purchase gear. Because an additional part of the catch

is allocated to those who possess gear, income is expected to increase accordingly. Moreover, the income level of these fishermen will also increase due to an overall expansion of the existing fishing effort within the region; the number of effective fishing days (the ratio between the number of fishermen and the number of boats) will be higher. In addition, those who are expected to buy one of those traditional sailboats (boat and gear owners) will substantially improve their income for similar reasons outlined earlier plus the fact that, as owners, they would receive the highest appropriable rent from existing fish resources.

7.29

The financial returns of those who own traditional sailboats and are expected to either buy improved sail boats or motorized boats will increase substantially due to an additional set of factors; for example, from fishing more days per year (both are more stable boats during the windy season) and from being able to carry a larger set of fishing gear (i.e., being larger boats, they can carry more “pontas” of net). The financial equity involved in purchasing those boats is expected to be equivalent to the sale value of the sailboat (i.e. C\$ 25,000). It is worth noting that

gross returns will be higher when purchasing a motorized boat because of the higher proportion of first-class fish caught.

7.30

Credit arrangements to purchase those boats or gear are highly subsidized--the nominal interest rate is 10%, while the inflation rate for 1980 is near 100% Consequently, the financial incentive to adopt improved technologies is there. However, because of the high subsidy element embodied in these loans, only a rate of return to the fishermen's input involved was calculated.

The Economic Analysis

7.31

This analysis was carried out under the following set of assumptions: an economic life of the project equal to ten years. Physical losses of output were assumed to decrease over time from 5% to 2% per year. However, it is expected that losses in quality will always take place; such losses in quality are implicitly accounted for by the type of crop portfolio assumed, namely, a very large proportion of third class fish. This production portfolio has been assumed to be constant over the entire life of the project. Subsistence, also called self-consumption, has been

assumed proportional to the number of fishing-days. For the boat owner, a percentage has been taken from the total production, while for the fishermen, selfconsumption is part of their total payments and is reflected in the O&M costs category. Phasing production levels was done assuming that new boat owners will take several years before they achieve maximum productivity. The economic life of sails was assumed to be six months, while the economic life of gear was two years (50% of the total gear is replaced every year). Salvage value for different investment items were assumed to be zero. Prices were assumed to be constant over the life of the project. Conversion factors for fish, diesel/gasoline, labor and wood were applied to different benefit and cost streams: these conversion factors are presented in Table 7-2. Conversion factors for other items have been assumed equal to unity. One hundred percent of total expenditure on extension and training has been attributed to fisheries investments. The same applies to expenditures in marketing and project administration; all are important expenditures to sustain productivity.

7.32

It is important to note that Table 7-2 shows project-specific

conversion factors. No other conversion factors are available. Other Bank rural development projects have used an average SCF of 1.15. The range of value for the fish conversion factors is wide depending upon the quality of fish (i.e., between 0.60 and 7.8). A weighted FCF (the quantity proportion of each quality fish used as proportions) was estimated to range between 1.1 and 1.53. All commodities have been assumed to be nontradable.

Table 7-2: CONVERSION FACTORS

Fishing Conversion Factor (FCF)	1.2
Gasoline Conversion Factor (GCF)	0.75
Wood Conversion Factor (WCF)	1
Labor Conversion Factor (LCF)	0.7
Equipment/Manufactured Goods (ECF)	1.1

7.33

The best estimate of the economic rate of return is 35 (for details, see Annex VII).

Sensitivity Analysis

7.34

Given the nature of this project and the data used for the economic analysis, particular attention was paid to calculate the switching values for all the parameters associated with the

list of assumptions outlined earlier. These values are presented in Tables 7-3 and 7-4.

Table 7-3: SWITCHING VALUES

Parameter	Switching Value
Benefits	33%
Investment Costs	455%
O&M Costs	69.20%
Total Costs	194%

Table 7-4: OTHER INDICATORS

Indicator	Value
NPV as percent of Present Costs	31%
Project NPV (12%)	167,499 (Cr\$'000)
Benefit/Cost Ratio	1.31

7.35

The project is sound; however, there are two categories of parameters that are important to study in detail: (a) those related to the benefit streams (i.e., value of production), and (b) delays in project implementation. The project seems to be very sensitive to both. The total value of production, as calculated in this project, is a function of (i) number of “pontas”, (ii) productivity per “pontas”, (iii) number of fishing days, (iv) self-consumption, (v) proportion of first-, second- and third-class of fish, and (vii) prices of first-, second- and third-class of fish. The technical

parameters were taken from the preparation report and revised during the appraisal mission. These technological parameters can change upward or downward depending on the effectiveness of the extension and training system and the quality of research and experiment, all of which will favor an upward shift in net productivity. The economic parameters like the demand for nets and the price of different classes of fish have to be monitored carefully. With regard to the demand for nets, this will depend on the price of petroleum-based products and the capacity of this project to expand the production frontier. Certainly the provision of improved sailboats would encourage fishermen to acquire more “pontas” of net. Finally, with regard to other inputs and output prices, the economic analysis has used the best available estimate. As stated earlier, because of the market’s ability to absorb a large quantity of fish, within and outside the state of Piauí, one would expect that fish prices at the beach will remain constant in real terms. In addition, economic prices used in the calculation of the ERR are affected by the value of the conversion factors and consequently, the monitoring unit should carefully study the changes in international trade for fish. A mid-term evaluation will be carried out at the end of the third project year.

Income and Income Distribution Impact

7.36

Fishermen's income in Piauí is mainly determined by the type of fishing vessel and gear used and by the ownership of that capital equipment, but little by the location of stocks and landing. Differences in income are also explained by differences in fishing methods, as, for example, fishermen who work on motorized vessels use pole and line as well as gill nets. Traditionally in Piauí, the catch of a fishing vessel is divided into three shares, of which the vessel gets 25%, the gear another 25% and the fishermen (including the owner when he fishes) the remaining 50%. This arrangement is used in the traditional and improved sailboat-fishing activities. Different arrangements are used in the motorized boats, where the owner provides all the gear and equipment, and where the bulk of the catch is first-class fish. Those payment schemes have to be adjusted by the number of effective fishing days each fisherman spends at sea, when the number of fishing days is very low, as stated in Section II and in Table 2-12. As explained in the following paragraphs, due to changes in ownership patterns and in technology, some of the productivity gains are expected to be redistributed among hired

fishermen (with or without gear).

7.37

Major gains in income levels and in income redistribution are expected from this project. These gains in overall welfare are expected to result from (i) an increase in the quantity of fishing effort--this will allow a substantial increase in the number of effective fishing days (i.e., the amount of effective income generated during the year); (ii) provision of additional sets of fishing gear--this will enable those who only supply their labor today to increase their share of existing fishing proceeds (i.e., a person with gear makes much more than one who does not); and (iii) improvement in the quality of part of the total fishing effort--this will enable many fishermen to fish during longer fishing season. Therefore, while individual fishermen's income improve by moving along the technological path proposed by this project, the project is planned to expand the productive capacity for all fishermen, thereby having a significant income redistribution effect.

7.38

There is only one group of fishermen--those who possess only gear

and work in fisheries as well as in agriculture (fishermen classified of “Tempo Parcial”)-whose income would seem to deteriorate in relative terms. However, it is important to note that income levels of those TP fishermen will increase due to improvements in agricultural productivity. Since accurate estimates of such productivity increase is not available, it is almost impossible to determine their overall welfare improvements resulting from the project.

7.39

With the existing data, Lorenz’s curves were drawn to illustrate the expected improvements in income distribution with the project (see Figure 7-2). The bottom left of the “with project” curve lies under the “without project” curve due to the factors outlined in the previous paragraph. However, what seems to be clear is the fact that substantial improvements in welfare-in absolute terms for all fishermen and in relative terms to the majority of fishermen-are expected to result from this project. One way to quantify this is by estimating the Gini coefficients “with” and “without” the project. The Gini coefficient “without” the project has been estimated at 0.488, and the Gini coefficient “with” the project is expected to be 0.241.

7.40

Given the fact that some fishermen work on other things, it is very difficult to predict with precision the net income impact of the project. Therefore, the unemployment pattern has to be developed during implementation. However, those who are expected to benefit the project would increase their incomes by at least 40%. Income statements for different categories of fishermen are presented in Annex VII.

Figure 7-2: INCOME DISTRIBUTION IMPACT OF THE FISHERIES PROJECT. LORENZ CURVES.

Fiscal Impact and Recurrent Costs

7.41

According to existing government rural development policies, fishermen are not expected to pay for expenditures in the areas of extension, research, social services and social infrastructure. However, the fishing villages often do contribute to the maintenance of much facilities once infrastructure is developed. Road construction which can be attributed to this component is very small; its construction and maintenance costs are expected to be recovered indirectly through various taxes and license fees on road users.

7.42

Project investment costs, such as boat and gear and those items that will be allocated to COPELCO, would be recovered from the fishermen through the credit system. The extent to which these costs will be recovered in real terms is difficult to estimate because of the current inflationary environment in Brazil and the government's policy of providing unindexed rural credit. Assuming a continuing inflation rate somewhat similar to the average of the last few years, real recovery of fishery

investment costs could be rather low. Although the increase in production by project beneficiaries would probably enable them to bear the burden of positive interest rates for credit received, the government has so far chosen, particularly in view of the relatively low incomes of the target beneficiaries for special programs, to maintain a considerable subsidy element in the rural credit component.

7.43

The costs of those items financed under “Fondo Perdido” are not fully included in the estimate of the economic rate of return. From the total cost of extension, training and technical assistance, only 50% is directly related to the productivity of fishing activity; the remaining 50% is related to improving the productivity of several other income-earning activities. Recurrent cost of all these items should decrease after Year 6 to keep only that level of expenditure which is necessary to maintain these estimated productivity growth rates.

7.44

These described recurrent costs will be recovered through taxes, particularly through the ICM (I posto de Circulação de

Mercadorias).

EMATER-PI

7.45

The project will be instrumental in expanding EMATER's sphere of action in the fishery sector. In the past, fishery-sector-related programs have been small, though the demand for technical assistance and training has grown substantially. The project would allocate US\$2.7 million, for a period of five year; the largest amount of funds will be allocated in Year 4. These funds will serve to hire the necessary personnel and equipment to increase fishermen income.

Net Impacts of Taxation

7.46

Since the project has included funds to improve processing within the state, the expected impact of ICM taxes is expected to be relatively high. However, several other factors may influence the net amount of ICM taxes collected due to the expansion of this project: (i) net trade balances with other states-available evidence shows that the larger the deficit is, the larger is the

amount of ICM collected; and (ii) degree of processing.

Employment and Nutrition Impact

7.47

It would be very difficult to realistically quantify those Piauienses, and those from neighboring states, who would benefit from increased employment and improved nutrition. The main objective here is to improve labor productivity of those engaged in fishing as well as of those involved in processing and marketing. In terms of effective man-year equivalents, the project creates 836 “new” jobs for those directly involved in harvesting the fish. However, it is expected that several jobs will be created at the beach level, in marketing and transport, and in the wholesaling and retailing of fish. The lack of alternative economic opportunities within Piauí’s fishery sector, except for those TP fishermen, has deteriorated the standard of living of many artisanal fishermen families. It would be the project’s overriding objective to rectify the sector’s structural deficiencies, and through the creation of the aforementioned investment opportunities-in harvesting, processing, marketing and distribution-to improve the overall sector’s performance

7.48

The nutritional impact of this project is expected to be substantial, although very difficult to quantify. The source of this institutional improvement will come, for the fishing family, from an important increase in income from fishing and other productive activities. The extension service is expected to provide assistance to other members of the fishing family, particularly to the fishermen's wives, enabling them to make the maximum use of existing natural resources available at the fishing village level (e.g., use of babassu nuts, horticulture). This training will also include courses in the art of weaving (e.g., carpets) and the fabrication of several artisanal products (e.g., use of shells), all of which are expected to increase their purchasing power.

7.49

The source of the nutritional impact for other people within and outside the state is expected to come from the distribution of a larger quantity of fish (quantity effect). This fish will be distributed fresh, smoked, salted, dried and in some other forms where most of the indigenously processed fish is expected to be shipped to rural areas. Also, this increased production may induce a higher substitution between fish and other relatively

more expensive sources of animal protein (e.g., beef). People outside the state, both in urban and rural areas, are expected to continue benefiting from Piauí's fish production.

Incremental Credit Requirements

7.50

The total cost of those items to be financed through the POLONORDESTE system, as presented in the project's cost table, overstates the total demand for credit. Given the terms and conditions of credit¹ outlined in Section V, repayments of the proposed loans to fishermen, COPELCO and other project beneficiaries go back to a "revolving fund" within the POLONORDESTE program and re-lent in subsequent years. For the first 5 years the total (net) demand for credit is estimated at Cr\$165 million. Given the long grace periods for fixed investments, total credit is very close to the net demand for credit for the first two to three years.

1

Vessels: 8 years, 2 grace, $i = 10\%$;

Gear: 2 years, -, $i = 10\%$;

Equipment: 12 years, 5 grace, $i = 10\%$;

Working Capital: 120 days, -, 10% .

Incremental Credit Requirements

7.51

The proposed project is expected to have a positive environmental impact. The scale of development of coastal fisheries would not alter negatively the ecological balance of existing fish resources. With the information that is available, the project has been formulated in such a way as to obtain a balance between fleet size and quality (productivity) and existing fisheries resources, thereby protecting the self-renewability nature of these resources. The project will provide consulting money for conducting a resource assessment activity under the direction of SUDEPE; this study will shed additional light on the state of fishery resources in the Piauí's coastal zone. The information made available by the end of the second year of the project will be carefully studied and, if necessary, changes in the size and quality of the fishing effort will be recommended. Finally, to avoid unnecessary pressures over existing resources by trawl fisheries, assurances have been given that the Código de Pesca will be strictly enforced to protect coastal fish resources from unnecessary overexploitation.

Project Impacts on Women

7.52

In fishing villages, women play a very important role. First, women repair nets and sails, thus increasing the economic life of fishing gear. Second, women expand the resource base of the fishing family by cultivating adjacent areas to their households- horticulture products as well as processed products from perennial crops, e.g., babassu and cashew. Third, women who have acquired some training produce artisanal products (e.g., mats, woven products, clothes) which expand and stabilize the fishing family's sources of income-particularly during the off-fishing season when fishermen have no economically active occupations. Finally, women from those fishing families dealing with the catch of mangrove crabs and shrimp act as processors and wholesalers of several products (see section on processing)- cooking, salting and drying are common activities in the area, benefiting an expanded consumption of the rural poor.

7.53

The project does not modify these activities; on the contrary, it encourages them in, at least, two different ways: (a) financing

a team of social workers to continue training fishermen's wives as well as children to maximize the use of available resources; and (b) opening a line of credit to processors-for cooking utensils, tables and equipment-and to intermediariesfor inputs and transport. The technical unit will have to put in some extra effort to make part of this program effective, since some of the abovementioned households are difficult to reach. Nevertheless, the important element is the fact that this project has considered the whole fishing family as part of it, both in the way the project was designed and for available sources of funds.

Risks

7.54

There are some risks involved in this project. Marketing and organization of fishing activities are the major factors affecting the risk associated with the project. The overall performance (managerial and commercial) of the cooperative will clearly set the stage for the implementation of this project. Technical assistance in marketing, administration, accounting, auditing and cooperativism are provided by the project. Also, the project provides the necessary equipment, enabling the coop to supply the fishermen with very important inputs (e.g., ice). This input

supply function should boost the number of participants in the coop.

7.55

The absorptive capacity of shipbuilding may pose some risks. The project is providing credit to purchase appropriate tools to increase the number of vessels that are, at present, constructed. This expected increase in productivity will not only serve in increasing the construction capacity for the incremental investment of this project, but also for future vessel replacement. With regard to building improved sailboats, no consultant time has been allocated, under the assumption that such technology will be easily absorbed by the shipbuilders. In the short term, this assumption may not hold.

7.56

EMATER's absorptive capacity to deal with the fisheries component may be affected by the need to deal with other components of the rural development project; the uncoordinated expansion, for example, of the agricultural component may cause some performance deterioration in this component (negative externalities).

7.57

Finally, fishermen may not be willing to increase their supply of labor; this way result from a highly productive leisure or because the individual fisherman does not foresee where to spend the money. References to this phenomenon are presented in the main text. To avoid this to happen, the project recognizes a built-in expenditure pattern which would absorb an unsatisfied supply of cash: (i) land purchase, (ii) development programs within the village (i.e., purchase and maintenance of public services like water supply and roads), and (iii) development programs within the fishery sector (i.e., operation and maintenance of investments and equipment).

7.58

To avoid these and other potential risks, the project has been designed in such a way as to increase the size and quality of the fishing effort slowly. Also, the project will be evaluated after two years of its implementation, at which time there will be an opportunity for redesigning any component of this project.

ANNEX I

ANNUAL OPERATING PLAN: YEAR 1 (POA-1)

1. The successful implementation of this experimental project will require careful annual planning and implementation. This annex focuses particularly on the operating plan for the first year of the project: POA-1.

2. To accomplish the project's targets set for the first year, the following aspects have to be taken into consideration: (a) shipbuilding, (b) contracting the gear, (a) allocating credit demands, (d) acquiring the equipment for the cooperative of Luis Correia, (e) contracting needed consultants, and (f) hiring the required extension personnel.

Shipbuilding

3. During the first year, the project proposed to finance the construction of 4 canoes, 31 traditional sailboats, 3 improved sailboats and 5 motorized boats. To accomplish such a target, shipbuilders have to be incorporated into the project and be provided with credit for purchasing new tools. The active

participation of shipbuilders early in the year (April 1981 or before) will allow them to acquire or contract the wood and buy the necessary materials (e.g., nails, wire).

4. If by the middle of the year there are some delays in implementation, priority should be given to the 4 canoes, 3 improved sailboats and the 5 motorized vessels. This is to say that part of the 31 traditional sailboats could be transferred to the second year of the project.

5. EMATER should hire at least one engineer with knowledge in vessel construction and design. Although the improved sailboats will not require much additional knowledge, it would be important to assist those shipbuilders who contract the improved sailboats.

Fishing Gear

6. It is expected that, as credit is made available, there will be a considerable demand for fishing gear and equipment. EMATER should start identifying those fishing families who are making and repairing nets. These nets can be made using local materials

(e.g., from palm trees) or nylon monofilament. This material seems to be readily available in Teresina and Parnaiba.

7. Fishermen, with MATER assistance, should 'contract the engine for their vessels with existing wholesalers. This should be made soon after the contract for the construction of the motorized boat takes place.

Credit

8. Local bank should be visited and an agreement reached with regard to the financing of nonmotorized vessels (as it is done right now), of motorized vessels (a credit to the cooperative) and of equipment for the cooperative.

9. The cost estimates for each item and the selection of contractors (local shipbuilders and equipment dealers) should be presented to the bank for approval. This process will avoid unnecessary delays in loan processing.

10. The credit to the cooperative of Luis Correia may be thought of as one or a few packages. One credit package may be equipment

and working capital, while the other package may be fishing vessels (including engines and safety equipment). In packaging those items subject to credit, the terms and conditions may change.

11. OCEPI technical assistance to the cooperative of Luis Correia may become an important instrument to facilitate decisions concerning credit, repayment periods and auditing of accounts.

Extension

12. The extension service is a key element, if not the most important, in implementing this project. EMATER will help in selecting-cum-informing the fishing communities, shipbuilders, merchants and processors of the availability of credit for different purposes. In conjunction with the banks, EMATER will set up the- credit application forms and establish the bridge between the fishermen and the banks.. A major emphasis will be given to those fishermen who belong to the cooperative.

Consultants

13. The project provides funds for hiring consultants in the areas of marketing, stock assessment, experiment and extension. Though the knowledge in these areas is extremely important, if delays are expected (particularly in the disbursement of funds), priorities must be given to the marketing and fish stock assessment studies.

14. It is expected that preliminary contact with FAO and consulting firms be done before negotiations so that execution of these components is not delayed. SUDEPE should coordinate the marketing study with CEPA, since this agency is also going to carry out a similar study for agricultural products and inputs. One survey questionnaire, done by CEPA, will be used for estimating demand functions. However, the marketing consultant financed by this project will deal with demand for inputs, production centers, prices, and with the institutional aspects of marketing.

Budgeting

15. The allocation of costs for different items during the first

year are presented in Tables I-1a through I-8d. The format issued here is the one required by the POLONORDESTE Program. Since the format is in Portuguese, a summary is presented in Table I-1:

Table I-1: ANNUAL OPERATING PLAN: YEAR 1, BY QUARTERS POA-1: 1981/82¹ (in Cr\$ '000)

Items	Qtr 1	Qtr 2	Qtr 3	Qtr 4	Total ²
Vessels/Equipment	2638.5	3265	4584.5	2628	13116
Merchant/Processors/Shipbuilders	1350	1400	1700	1350	5800
Extension/Technical Assistance	2831.3	3077.9	4241.2	2571.3	12721.8
Experiment/Research	2318.2	2362.5	1598.2	921.1	7200
Coop/Equipment/Work Capital/Others	3093.3	4096.1	5973.6	2372.3	15355.3
Coop/Technical Assistance	219	262.5	359.5	209	1050
Consulting	5572.8	1238.4	1857.6	619.2	9288
Administration	280.3	332	435.5	280.3	1328.2
TOTAL	18303.4	16034.4	20750.1	10951.2	65859.3

¹These figures are in constant terms. In nominal terms, the total request should be doubled (100% inflation) to Cr\$131.7 million.

²The difference between these figures and those appearing in the cost table is due to rounding errors.

Table I-1a

IDENTIFICAÇÃO	PROGRAMA	ANO	
	POLONORDESTE	ABR/MAY/JUN	
		JUL/AGO/SEP	
		JAN/FEB/MAR	
TITULO DO PROJETO			
PDRI VALE DO PARNAÍBA			
TITULO DO SUBPROJETO			
DESENVOLVIMENTO DA PESCA ARTESANAL / INVERSÕES EM BARCOS E EQUIPAMENTOS DE PESCA			
ORGÃO RESPONSÁVEL:			
ENDERECO			
ORGÃO (S) EXECUTOR (ES):			
ENDERECO (S): Agentes Financeiros (BB, BNB, BEP)			
ÁREA DE ATUAÇÃO SUBPROJETO:			
Parnaíba			
Luís Correia			
OBJETIVOS:			
Dotar os agentes financeiros de recursos necessários a introdução de equipamentos de captura e embarcações de acordo com as necessidade estabelecidas no projeto			

Table I-1b

RECURSOS FINANCEIROS		TRIMESTRE														TOTAL			
		ABR-JUN		JUL-SEP		OUT-DEZ		JAN-MAR		%		P		R		%			
		P	R	P	R	P	R	P	R	P	R	P	R	P	R	P	R		
ELEMENTO DE DESPESA																			
PESSOALE ENCARGOS SOCIAIS		P																	
		R																	
MATERIAL DE CONSUMO		P																	
		R																	
SERVIÇOS DE TERCEIROS		P																	
		R																	
ENCARGOS DIVERSOS		P																	
		R																	
OBRAS PÚBLICAS		P																	
		R																	
EQUIPAMENTOS E INSTALAÇÕES		P																	
		R																	
EQUIPAMENTOS DE SEGURANÇA		P	175000		200000			300000			175000								850000
		R																	
AQUISIÇÃO DE BARCOS		P	372500		447500			627500			357500								1805000
		R																	
AQUISIÇÃO DE APARELHOS DE PESCA		P	2091000		2617500			3657000			2095500								10461000
		R																	
TOTAL POR PERÍODO		P	2638500		3265000			4585500			2628000								13116000
		R																	

OBS 1 - OS PERCENTUAIS SERÃO CALCULADOS EM RELAÇÃO AO PREVISTO E REALIZADO ACUMULADOS

OBS 2 - AS LINHAS "R" DA COLUMNA TOTAL SOMENTE SERÃO PREENCHIDAS QUANDO O GASTO TOTAL DO ELEMENTO DE DESPESA ESTIVER EFETIVADO AO FIM DOS 4 TRIMESTRES

Table I-1c

SUBPROJETO: METAS (ATIVIDADES)	DISCRIMINAÇÃO	QUANTIDADE												VALOR TOTAL ²	%	P	R		
		ABR-JUN		JUL-SEP		OUT-DEZ		JAN-MAR		TOTAL ¹		P						R	
		%	P	R	%	P	R	%	P	R	%	P	R					%	P
		1			1		1		1		1		4						
	P																		
	R																		
	P	8			7		11		5		31								
	R																		
	P	-			1		1		1		3								
	R																		
	P	7			8		12		7		34								
	R																		
	P	3			3		3		3		12								
	R																		
	P	298			376		530		288		1492								
	R																		
	P	60			60		60		120		300								
	R																		
	P																		
	R																		
	P																		
	R																		

SIGLA
FLS

OBS 1 - AS LINHAS "R" SOMENTE DEVERÃO SER PREENCHIDAS AO FIM DOS 4 TRIMESTRES OU DA ATIVIDADE

Table I-1d

SUBPROJETO						
METAS (INFRAESTRUTURA)						
DISCRIMINAÇÃO	MUNICIPIO	QUANT.	DATAS		VALOR TOTAL Cr\$ 1,00	
			INICIO	TÉRMINO		
			P			
			R			
			P			
			R			
			P			
			R			
			P			
			R			
			P			
			R			

Table I-2a

IDENTIFICAÇÃO	PROGRAMA	ANO	SIGLA
	POLONORDESTE	ABR/MAY/JUN	FLS
		JUL/AGO/SEP	
		JAN/FEB/MAR	
TITULO DO PROJETO			
PDRI VALE DO PARNAÍBA			
TITULO DO SUBPROJETO			
DESENVOLVIMENTO DA PESCA ARTESANAL / CONSULTORIA AO PROJETO			
ORGÃO RESPONSÁVEL: SUDEPE/COREG-PI			
ENDERECO: Rua Taumaturgo de Azevedo, 2315 - Bloco 02, Sala304 - Teresina-PI			
ORGÃO (S) EXECUTOR (ES): SUDEPE/COREG-PI			
ENDERECO: Rua Taumaturgo de Azevedo, 2315 - Bloco 02, Sala304 - Teresina-PI - FAO - ROMA			
ÁREA DE ATUAÇÃO SUBPROJETO:			
Parnaíba			
Luís Correia			
OBJETIVOS:			
Assistir tecnicamente o projeto			

Table I-1c

SUBPROJETO: METAS (ATIVIDADES)	DISCRIMINAÇÃO	QUANTIDADE												VALOR TOTAL ²	%	P	R		
		ABR-JUN		JUL-SEP		OUT-DEZ		JAN-MAR		TOTAL ¹		P						R	
		%	P	R	%	P	R	%	P	R	%	P	R					%	P
	P			1			1							2			1857600		
	R																		
	P		1											1			1857600		
	R																		
	P		1											1			1238400		
	R																		
	P		1											1			1238400		
	R																		
	P		2		1				1					5			33096000		
	R																		
	P																		
	R																		
	P																		
	R																		
	P																		
	R																		

SIGLA
FLS

OBS 1 - AS LINHAS "R" SOMENTE DEVERÃO SER PREENCHIDAS AO FIM DOS 4 TRIMESTRES OU DAATIVIDADE

Table I-2d

SUBPROJETO						
METAS (INFRAESTRUTURA)						
DISCRIMINAÇÃO	MUNICIPIO	QUANT.		DATAS		VALOR TOTAL Cr\$ 1,00
				INICIO	TÉRMINO	
			P			
			R			
			P			
			R			
			P			
			R			
			P			
			R			
			P			
			R			

Table I-3a

IDENTIFICAÇÃO	PROGRAMA	ANO	SIGLA
	POLONORDESTE	ABR/MAY/JUN	FLS
		JUL/AGO/SEP	
		JAN/FEB/MAR	
TITULO DO PROJETO			
PDRI VALE DO PARNAÍBA			
TITULO DO SUBPROJETO			
DESENVOLVIMENTO DA PESCA ARTESANAL / EXT- ASSIST. TÉCNICA PESQUEIRA			
ORGÃO RESPONSÁVEL: SUDEPE/COREG-PI			
ENDERECO: Rua Taumaturgo de Azevedo, 2315 - Bloco 02, Sala304 - Teresina-PI			
ORGÃO (S) EXECUTOR (ES): EMATER-PI			
ENDERECO: Rua Coelho Rodrigues, 1647 - Teresina PI			
ÁREA DE ATUAÇÃO SUBPROJETO:			
Parnaíba			
Luís Correia			
OBJETIVOS:			
Prestar assistência técnica e extensão pesqueira aos pescadores beneficiarios do projeto e sus familias.			

Table I-3b

RECURSOS FINANCEIROS	ELEMENTO DE DESPESA	TRIMESTRE												TOTAL	%	P
		ABR-JUN		JUL-SEP		OUT-DEZ		JAN-MAR		P		R				
		%	P	R	%	P	R	%	P	R	%	P	R			
	P	2044820		2044820		2044821		2044820		2044820		2044820		8179281		
	R															
	P	143200		454000		1375600		243200		2216000						
	R															
	P	79429		274286		434002		79429		867146						
	R															
	P	-		-		-		-		-						
	R															
	P	-		-		-		-		-						
	R															
	P	102666		240832		267166		152666		763330						
	R															
	P	410000		-		-		-		410000						
	R															
	P	19200		24000		33600		19200		96000						
	R															
	P	32000		40000		56000		32000		160000						
	R															
	P	2831315		3077938		4241188		2571315		12721756						
	R															

OBS 1 - OS PORCENTUAIS SERÃO CALCULADOS EM RELAÇÃO AO PREVISTO E REALIZADO ACUMULADOS

OBS 2 - AS LINHAS "R" DA COLUMNA TOTAL SOMENTE SERÃO PREENCHIDAS QUANDO O GASTO TOTAL DO ELEMENTO DE DESPESA ESTIVER EFETIVADO AO FIM DOS 4 TRIMESTRES

Table I-3c

RECURSOS FINANCEIROS	ELEMENTO DE DESPESA	TRIMESTRE												TOTAL	%	VALOR TOTAL	%	P	R
		ABR-JUN		JUL-SEP		OUT-DEZ		JAN-MAR		P		R							
		%	P	R	%	P	R	%	P	R	%	P	R						
	P	69		86		122			69					346					
	R																		
	P	69		86		122			69					346					
	R																		
	P	16		20		88			16					140		48000			
	R																		
	P	16		20		88			16					140		48000			
	R																		
	P	10		-		-			-					10		410000			
	R																		
	P																		
	R																		
	P																		
	R																		
	P																		
	R																		

OBS 1 - OS PERCENTUAIS SERÃO CALCULADOS EM RELAÇÃO AO PREVISTO E REALIZADO ACUMULADOS

OBS 2 - AS LINHAS "R" DA COLUMNA TOTAL SOMENTE SERÃO PREENCHIDAS QUANDO O GASTO TOTAL DO ELEMENTO DE DESPESA ESTIVER EFETIVADO AO FIM DOS 4 TRIMESTRES

Table I-3d

SUBPROJETO						
METAS (INFRAESTRUTURA)						
DISCRIMINAÇÃO	MUNICIPIO	QUANT.	DATAS		VALOR TOTAL Cr\$ 1,00	
			INICIO	TÉRMINO		
			P			
			R			
			P			
			R			
			P			
			R			
			P			
			R			
			P			
			R			

Table I-3e

SIGLA

FLS

PRE-REQUISITOS E INFORMAÇÕES ADICIONAIS¹

Serão contratados pelo projeto:

- 04 Engs. de Pesca
- 03 Assistentes sociais
- 02 Técnicos em pesca (NM)
- 02 Extensionistas sociais (NM)
- 03 Auxiliares administrativos

¹USE ESTA FICHA P/INFORMAR: a) AÇÕES PRELIMINARES A EXECUÇÃO DO SUS PROJETO
b) RAÇÕES QUE JUSTIFIQUEM O ATRASO NA EXECUÇÃO FÍSICO-FINANCEIRA DO SUS PROJETO
c) OUTRAS INFORMAÇÕES CONSIDERADAS RELEVANTES SOBRE O SUS PROJETO

Table I-4a

			SIGLA
			FLS
IDENTIFICAÇÃO	PROGRAMA	ANO	
	POLONORDESTE	ABR/MAY/JUN	
		JUL/AGO/SEP	
		JAN/FEB/MAR	
TÍTULO DO PROJETO			
PDRI VALE DO PARNAÍBA			
TÍTULO DO SUBPROJETO			
DESENVOLVIMENTO DA PESCA ARTESANAL / ASS. TÉCNICA / JURÍDICA / CONTÁBIL A COPELCO			
ORGÃO RESPONSÁVEL: SUDEPE/COREG-PI			
ENDERECO: Rua Taumaturgo de Azevedo, 2315 - Bloco 02, Sala304 - Teresina-PI			
ORGÃO (S) EXECUTOR (ES): OCEPI			
ENDERECO: Rua Taumaturgo de Azevedo, 2315 - Bloco 02, Sala304 - Teresina-PI			
ÁREA DE ATUAÇÃO SUBPROJETO:			
Parnaíba			
Luís Correia			
OBJETIVOS:			
Prestar assistência técnica, jurídica, contábil e gerencial a COPELCO.			

Table I-4d

SUBPROJETO						
METAS (INFRAESTRUTURA)						
DISCRIMINAÇÃO	MUNICIPIO	QUANT.	DATAS		VALOR TOTAL Cr\$ 1,00	
			INICIO	TÉRMINO		
			P			
			R			
			P			
			R			
			P			
			R			
			P			
			R			
			P			
			R			

ANNEX II

DRAFT TERMS OF REFERENCES FOR CONSULTANTS

1. The project is expected to finance 27 man-months of consultants, distributed as follows: (a) 4 man-months for marketing, (b) 7 man-months for fish stock assessment, (c) 10 man-months for extension, (d) 6 man-months for experiment, and (e) 5 man-months for shipbuilding (see Table 11-1). This section presents a basic outline for the Terms of References.

Table II-1: CONSULTANTS (ma-months)

ITEMS	Years					TOTAL
	I	II	III	IV	V	
Marketing	3	1	-	-	-	4
Stock assessment	3	3	1	-	-	7
Extension	2	2	2	2	2	10
Experiment	2	1	1	1	1	6
Shipbuilding	5	-	-	-	-	5
TOTAL	15	7	4	3	3	32

Marketing

2. The objective of this activity is to acquire systematic knowledge on all marketing-related aspects of fish and fish products. The consultant should provide the analytic framework and put this framework into operation, so the team will be able to know

about demand functions by income groups and by subregion (i.e., rural versus urban), demand projections, prices and price fluctuations, consumption centers, production centers, and the like. The consultant should also study the institutional aspects of marketing and the profit margins, and provide the cooperative of Luis Correia with a sound marketing strategy.

3. Most data on demand functions and structure should come from the CEPA's Marketing Study, financed under another component¹. However, the data processing and the report writing will be done by the consultant.

4. The work should start in August 1981.

Stock Assessment

5. The objective of this activity is to greatly improve current knowledge on existing fish species in the Piauí coastal areas.

6. The consultant should establish and provide a methodology, define the stock assessment models, study existing data, define the overall programming for future years and draft a final

¹ A detailed outline for the study is presented in Attachment I of this Annex.

document. This exercise will be repeated for a period of three years, at which time a local team (i.e., SUDEPE) will take up the study. During the first year, biostatistic data should be collected and reported on the most important fish species.

7. This stock assessment activity should be coordinated very closely with the consulting work on experimenting with different sets of fishing gear.

8. It is expected that perhaps TAO/SUDEPE should form a team to carry out this study. The study should start on April 1, 1981.

Experiment

9. The objective of this activity is to establish different productivity parameters for existing and improved fishing gear;

10. This activity requires the establishment of a methodology, definitions of gear size, data collection and analysis and, then, the redesign, if necessary, of existing gear. These experiments should be carried out in close coordination with the stock assessment activities. It is expected that a report (preliminary and final) will

be drafted every year. During the first year, experiments and data on different types of gillnets (e.g., differentiated by size, position while fishing) for species like sea bass, king mackerel, tarpon and catfish.

11. Most probably, a FAO/SUDEPE team will be very effective in carrying out this work.

12. This work should start April 1, 1981.

Extension and Technical Assistance

13. The objective of this activity is to improve the approach, data system, and evaluation of extension and technical assistance 'barried out by EMATER in the coastal areas. The outcome of this exercise will certainly have an impact on other EMATER activities (e.g., agriculture extension).

14. The consultant should review and analyze existing reporting systems and review current administrative and monitoring procedures. A proposal and evaluation of some activities related to such proposal must take place. This work can be done in

stages, beginning with an overall analysis of present methods, followed by a proposal and finishing with the application and evaluation of such proposal.

15. During the first year it is expected that technical and credit assistance will be given to at least 190 fishermen. Technical assistance includes fishing technology, marketing and coop principles.

16. It is expected that a private consultant might do this job.

17. This activity should start April 1, 1981.

Shipbuilding

18. The objective of this activity is to train existing shipbuilders and one EMATER staff member in building the new improved sailboats. Clear improvement can be achieved with the introduction of the centered-board type of whale-boat. The consultant is expected to train at least four shipbuilders and set up a training scheme to train the remaining shipbuilders. The consultant will also advise on the type of tools that need to be

introduced within this subsector. Finally, the consultant should test some of the improved sailboats.

19. For a sample of drawings, see Attachment 1I to this Annex. This attachment has been taken from Modern Fishing Boats of the World, Volume I, pages 51-72, 73-79 and 203-210.

20. It is expected that a private consultant or FAO may participate in the project. This activity should start on April 1, 1981.

ATTACHMENT I

PIAUI FISH MARKETING STUDY: SUGGESTED OUTLINE

I. DEVELOPMENT FRAMEWORK

a. Policy

b. Piaui's Fishing Industry

II. INVESTMENT AND DEVELOPMENT OF PROCESSING, MARKETING AND DISTRIBUTION

a. The Structure of Subsectors

b. Marketing and Distribution

i. Overview

ii. Target Groups and Distribution Strategy

- Wholesalers

- Retailers

- Public Marketing

- Urban versus Rural

c. Cost Structures

i. Production and Harvesting

ii. Beach Handling

iii. Processing Costs

- Individual Fishing Family

- COPELCO

IV. Distribution Costs

- Private Middlemen
- COPELCO
- Others

d. Projections

e. Development Organization

i. Structure

ii. Performance

iii. Prices and Pricing Policy

iv. Profit Margins

III. ARTISANAL FISHERIES DEVELOPMENT AND MARKETING DEVELOPMENT

a. Consumption and Future Demand

1. By Type of Fish

ii. By Income Group

iii. By Urban/Rural

iv. By Other Metropolitan and Rural Areas in the Northeast

b. Future Supply

i. Supply Projections

ii. Supply Bottlenecks

c. Nutritional Impacts

i. Protein-Calorie Intake

ii. Volume of Fish Protein Compared with Other Sources of Animal Protein

d. Factors Determining Marketing and Distribution Capacity

i. Role of Income

ii. Role of Population Growth

iii. Role of Prices

iv. Role of Tastes

v. Other Factors

IV. POLICY IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

-----Dr. Alfredo Sfeir-Younis
Dzambling Cho Tab Khen
World Bank, 1981-----